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**Republic of Iraq
Ministry of Higher Education
and Scientific Research
Foundation of Technical Education
College of Health and Medical Technology/Baghdad**

Humoral and Cell Mediated Immuno-Modulatory Trend in *Helicobacter pylori*-Induced Gastrointestinal Diseases

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO
THE COLLEGE COUNCIL OF HEALTH AND MEDICAL
TECHNOLOGY AS PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF
TECHNOLOGY IN MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE
TECHNOLOGY**

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بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

«وَلِكُلِّ دَرَجَاتٍ مِمَّا عَمِلُوا وَمَا رَبُّكَ بِغَافِلٍ عَمَّا يَعْمَلُونَ»

صَدَقَ اللَّهُ الْعَلِيِّ الْعَظِيمِ

سورة الأنعام/الآية ١٣٢

I can see no person, writes a book, in a day; unless the next day, says: Oh, if this had been changed it would have been improved, if this had been expanded it would have been preferable, if this had been put earlier it would have been better and if this had been omitted it would have been nicer.

This is a great "lesson", and a proof that there is no perfection in the human kind.

Al-Imad Al-Asphahany
a Philosopher

DEDICATION

To the owner of the greatest honor, the venerable prophet, our prophet Mohammed the messenger of Allah (Allah pray and peace upon him and his family), and I request his intercession in the doomsday, to his chaste sinless household, and his kind companions.

To the scion of prophecy house, the lion-hearted imam, the owner of the epoch and this time, to the all religious leaders and good righteous people.

To ... my father ... (mercy of Allah on him and made the paradise his home).

To ... my mother ... who I am shading in her appeal, I ask long life for her ,and giving her the best of what he gave to mother from her son.

To ... the sources of science and knowledge my professors.

To ... the origin of loyalty my brothers.

To ... the piece of my eye my aunt.

To ... all who helped me in my humble research.

To them I dedicate what accommodate darling Allah sincerely and gratitude.

Hassan Alasady

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Hassan Alasady

SUMMARY

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) infection has a world wide distribution. The bacteria colonize more than half of the world population and consider the main cause of gastritis, peptic ulceration, gastric adenocarcinoma and gastric lymphoma. The host immune response is unable to clear the infection and may actually contribute to the associated pathogenesis, also the bacterial virulent factors had certain role in the pathogenicity of infection as it was stated by limited studies that the Cytotoxin associated gene A (*CagA*) positive strains are possibly associated with severe infections.

The present study was designed to frame out in a panoramic manner the nature of the *H. pylori*-associated diseases among a group of Iraqi patients. This includes the estimation of the prevalence rate of *H. pylori* infectivity among the patients underwent oesophageo-gastro-duodeno-scopy (OGD) and healthy people. This rate of *H. pylori* infectivity and their association with the disease severity was correlated with many disease activity markers as serum IL-17A level, peripheral blood Treg cell count %, histopathology findings, serum parietal cells autoantibody (PCA) frequency and level and bacterial strain type in reference to the presence or absence of *CagA* as virulence factor. Inter-correlations were also applied between each of the disease activity markers to elucidate the mutual effects on each others.

Sixty patients attending the Endoscopic Unit at Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital, during the period between September 2012 and February 2013, with age range of 18-80 years, and 30 apparently healthy individuals (negative control) with age range of 18-65 years were enrolled in this study after passing the gate of this study exclusion criteria. Both patients and negative control

(NC) were subjected to questionnaire data sheet and then each patient was subjected to OGD and 2-4 mucosal pinch biopsy sampling. From each biopsy, stained slides were prepared for histopathology examination for evaluation of gastritis and demonstration of spiral bacteria. Peripheral blood was collected from each subject of study groups by vein puncture which were divided into two parts; one for flow cytometry count of CD4⁺ CD25⁺ Treg cells, and one for serological tests, which included; immuno-chromatography *H. pylori* Abs combo rapid test, IgG anti-*H. pylori* Abs test, IgG anti-*CagA* Abs test, IgG-PCA test and IL-17A test using ELISA technique.

According to the classification criteria as it is mentioned in the materials and methods and primary endoscopic and histopathological diagnosis the patients were classified into 53 *H. pylori* associated patients (HPP) including gastritis patients (GS)=28, gastric ulcer patients (GU)=8 and duodenal ulcer patients (DU)=17, and 7 non-*H. pylori*-associated patients or positive control patients (PC) including gastritis patients (GS)=4, gastric ulcer patients (GU)=0 and duodenal ulcer patients (DU)=3. Epigastric pain/heart burn and nausea/vomiting were the highest frequencies of signs and symptoms among HPP and PC, whereas diarrhea was the lowest one among both groups. The differences in the presenting symptoms between the two groups were not significant ($p>0.05$), except for weight loss, a finding that was true for all HPP subgroups. Concerning the histopathological findings, the frequencies of active chronic gastritis, intestinal metaplasia and bacterial colonization were significantly ($p<0.05$) higher in HPP group compared to PC group, but there were no significant differences ($p>0.05$) in the frequencies of each type of histological gastritis among the HPP subgroups. In contrast to this, the frequency of intestinal metaplasia was significantly ($p<0.05$) higher within GU

subgroup compared to other HPP subgroups, whereas the frequency of bacterial colonization was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower within DU subgroup compared to other HPP subgroups. The frequencies and/or mean titer of IgG anti-*H. pylori* Abs and PCA were significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated in HPP group compared to controls. No significant differences ($p > 0.05$) was noticed between GS and GU subgroups regarding the PCA positive frequency and mean titer. However, DU subgroup exhibited a significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower frequency of PCA positive results in comparison to other HPP subgroups. The frequencies and mean count/titer of peripheral blood Treg cells and serum IL-17A level were revealed a significant ($p < 0.05$) elevation in HPP group compared to NC group, but no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) was reported for these markers among the HPP subgroups as well as between PCA positive and negative cases. T regulatory cells: IL-17A ratio was increased within HPP in comparison to both control groups. The difference in frequency between $CagA^-$ and $CagA^+$ was significant in HPP and NC groups ($p < 0.05$), which was true for HPP subgroups, except DU which exhibited a non-significant result ($p > 0.05$). However, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was noticed between the $CagA^+$ and $CagA^-$ strains concerning the above mentioned parameters, except for the PCA positivity which was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher among $CagA^-$ subjects than $CagA^+$ subjects and IgG anti-*H. pylori* positivity which exhibited an inverse result. There were no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) for all immunological markers used by this study in the presence or absence of intestinal metaplasia and type of histological gastritis, but a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was noticed in bacterial visibility between positive and negative PCA results. No significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was reported between the

frequency of bacterial visibility (colonization) and the presence and absence of intestinal metaplasia for all types of histological gastritis.

In conclusion, the frequency of *H. pylori* infection in apparently healthy and/or asymptotically infected individuals whom included in this study was 53.3%, which is much lower than those in Asian and non-Asian studied populations. On the other hand, the rate was 88.3% in symptomatically infected individuals whom attended above mentioned hospital, which is similar to those in most of Asian and non-Asian studied populations. Epigastric pain and heart burn are the most common signs/symptoms among *H. pylori*-associated and non-*H. pylori* associated gastro-enteropathy. On the other hand, weight loss was the only one with significant difference between gastro-enteropathy groups, a conclusion that was true for HPP subgroups. Detection of IgG anti-*H. pylori* in the serum of GIT patients is helpful in the avoidance of more invasive diagnostic tests as endoscopy and biopsy, but the level of IgG anti-*H. pylori* Abs in the serum do not predict the occurrence of peptic ulcers or the density of *H. pylori* colonization. Most HPP subjects exhibited a high level of serum IL-17A and peripheral blood Treg cells counts. The Treg:IL-17A ratio is higher in HPP group than PC and NC groups, which concludes an ineffective immune response in the HPP due to the Treg count dominance over the IL-17A titer. The prevalence of PCA was 20% in healthy and/or asymptomatic infected people and 30.2% in *H. pylori*-associated patients which point out a considerable positive relationship between *H. pylori* infection and gastric autoimmunity. The presence of PCA may be coincides with a protective level of DU development. Peripheral blood Treg count and serum IL-17A level expressed no significant effect on PCA positivity, bacterial load, intestinal metaplasia and type of histological gastritis. The prevalence of IgG

anti-*CagA* among positive IgG anti-*H. pylori* Iraqi people was 37.3% which is much lower than most other global studies. The presence of *CagA*⁺ strain of *H. pylori* is not enough for the prediction of the type of *H. pylori*-associated disease as well as the severity of the disease. However, *CagA*⁺ strains play a role in the modulation of the immune response through elucidation of high titer of IgG anti-*H. pylori*. *Helicobacter pylori* strain type has little and not significant effect on the IL-17A level and Treg cells counts in patients with *H. pylori* associated diseases. Cytotoxin associated gene A has no role in the induction of *H. pylori*-related auto-immune gastritis and not correlated with certain histopathological findings such as the type of histological gastritis, presence or absent of intestinal metaplasia and the bacterial density in the gastric stained sections. The mentioned histopathological findings were not correlated with IgG anti-*H. pylori* level or PCA positivity, except the bacterial colonization has certain role in induction of the mentioned autoimmune disease.

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	الخلاصه	

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Explanation
AP-1	Activator Protein1
ACG	Active Chronic Gastritis
ACSG	Active Chronic Superficial Gastritis
ATPase	Adenosine Triphosphatase
Ab	Antibody
Ag	Antigen
APCs	Antigen-presenting Cells
AIG	Autoimmune Gastritis
β	Beta
BabA	Blood Group Ag Binding Adhesion
BMI	Body Mass Index
Cag-PAI	Cag Pathogenicity Island
Treg	CD4 ⁺ CD25 ⁺ T-regulatory Cell
C°	Centigrade
cm	Centimeter
CG	Chronic Gastritis
CSG	Chronic Superficial Gastritis
CD	Cluster of Differentiation
cAMP	Cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate
CTLA-4	Cytotoxic T-Lymphocyte Antigen 4
<i>CagA</i>	Cytotoxin-associated Gene A
DCs	Dendritic Cells
DNase	Deoxyribonuclotidase
DNA	Deoxyriboucleic Acid
DU	Duodenal Ulcer
EIA	Enzyme Immunoassays
ELISA	Enzyme-linked Immune-sorbent Assay
EDTA	Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid
Fig	Figure
FC	Flow Cytometry
FITC	Fluorescein Isothiocyanate

FOXP ₃	Forkhead box P ₃
FR	Frequency
GORD	Gasrto-oesophageal Reflux Disease
GU	Gastric Ulcer
GS	Gastritis
GIT	Gastrointestinal Tract
gm	Gram
HpaA	<i>H. pylori</i> Adhesin A
HPP	<i>H. pylori</i> Associated Patients
H. and E.	Haematoxylin and Eosin
HSPA	Heat Shock Proteins A
HSPB	Heat Shock Proteins B
<i>H. pylori</i>	<i>Helicobacter pylori</i>
<i>Hp</i>	<i>Helicobacter pylori</i>
HRP	Horseradish Peroxidase
hrs	Hours
IL-2R α	IL-2 Receptor Alpha Subunit
iDC	Immature Dendritic Cell
IgA	Immunoglobulin A
IgG	Immunoglobulin G
IgM	Immunoglobulin M
IDO	Indoleamine 2, 3-dioxygenase
<i>IceA</i>	Induced by Contact with Epithelium Gene A
iTreg	Induced Treg
IFN- γ	Interferon Gamma
IL	Interleukin
IL-23r	Interleukin-23 Receptor
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
IM	Intestinal Metaplasia
kDa	kilo Dalton
Le	Lewis
LPS	Liopolysaccharide
MHC	Major-histocompatibility-complex

MP	Membrane Protein
μl	Microliter
μm	Micrometer
ml	Milliliter
min	Minute
MAPKs	Mitogen Activated Protein Kinases
MCA	Monoclonal Antibody
MALT	Mucosa-associated Lymphoid Tissue
MPO	Myeloperoxidase
nm	Nanometer
nTreg	Naturally Occurring Treg
-ve	Negative
NC	Negative Control
NBF	Neutral Buffered Formalin
<i>Hp</i> -NAP	Neutrophil Activating Protein of <i>H. pylori</i>
NSAIDs	Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs
NS	Not Significant
NF-κB	Nuclear Factor-kappa B
Nod1	Nucleotide-binding Oligomerization Domain Protein 1
N _o	Number
n	Number
OGD	Oesophageo-gastro-duodeno-scopy
OD	Optical Density
PCA	Parietal Cell Autoantibody
PU	Peptic Ulcer
PUD	Peptic Ulcer Disease
%	Percent
PB	Peripheral Blood
PBMC	Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cell
PE	Phycoerythrin
pg	Picogram
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction

PMN	Polymorph Nuclear
+ve	Positive
PC	Positive Control
PPIs	Proton Pump Inhibitors
ROR γ t	Retinoid-related Orphan Receptor γ
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
sIgA	Secretory IgA
SabA	Sialic Acid Binding Adhesion
SHP 2	Src Homology 2 Domian-containing Protein
SD	Standard Deviation
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
Th	T Helper
TMB	Tetramethylbenzidine
TLRs	Toll-like Receptors
TGF- β	Transforming Growth Factor β
TNF- α	Tumor Necrosis Factor Alpha
TRAIL-DR5	Tumor-necrosis-factor-related Apoptosis-inducing Ligand-death Receptor 5
U/ml	Unit/Milliliter
<i>VacA</i>	Vacuolating Cytotoxin A
WHO	World Health Organization

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CHAPTER ONE
INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori is one of the most common chronic bacterial infections in humans effecting more than half of the people in whole world and is recognized as a major etiological factor for several gastro-duodenal diseases, including active chronic gastritis (ACG), gastric ulcers (GU), duodenal ulcers (DU), gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphomas and distal gastric cancer. All people colonized by *H. pylori* will virtually develop gastritis; however, only 15% of these colonized develop disease [1]. Pathogenesis depends upon strain virulence, host genetic susceptibility and environmental co-factors [2].

Many putative virulence factors have been identified in *H. pylori* that contribute to its pathogenesis, most important among them is the 120-kilo Dalton (kDa) *CagA* [2] and hence according to this virulence factor, *H. pylori* strains have been divided into types I and II. Type I strains express *CagA* ($CagA^+$) but type II strains do not express *CagA* ($CagA^-$) [3]. About 60 to 80% of *H. pylori* strains in the world can produce *CagA* [4] which has been identified as a virulence marker of *H. pylori* to induce more severe mucosal damages and inflammatory responses [5] as well as is associated with a higher gastric mucosal infiltration of neutrophils [6].

Helicobacter pylori infection triggers a vigorous immune response, resulting in high titers of *H. pylori*-specific antibodies (Abs) and this response is not sufficient for eradication of the pathogen and when remaining untreated with antibiotics, infection will remain for life [7]. Evidence suggests that *H. pylori* pathogenesis results primarily from the immune response and thus understanding how this immune response is initiated and controlled is critical. The roles of the T helper (Th) 17 and $CD4^+CD25^+$ T-regulatory cell (Treg) populations

during *H. pylori* infections have been debated recently. The Th17 cell is involved in promoting chronic inflammation; the Treg cell, in contrast, regulates host immune responses. Currently it is unknown if a Th17 response or a Treg response underlies the ineffective immune response to *H. pylori* [8].

The regulatory role of interleukin- (IL)17 in the synthesis of IL-8 by gastric mononuclear and epithelial cells in the *H. pylori*-driven inflammation is discussed by some authors [9 and 10] who found that a significant correlation was seen between IL-17 and IL-8 levels in the site of *H. pylori*-positive GU. However, the factors involved in the control of IL-17 production in *H. pylori*-associated gastritis are yet unclear except in one study which found that serum IL-17 expression was influenced by the *CagA* factor among *H. pylori* DU patients [11].

The role of other T lymphocyte subpopulation as Treg in preventing autoimmune diseases as well as in the suppression of tumor immunity and induction of dominant transplantation tolerance is well established [12]. However, the role of these Treg cells in *H. pylori* infection is poorly defined. In one study, it was concluded that Treg cells reduce immunopathology in *H. pylori* infection, possibly by reducing the activation of interferon gamma (IFN- γ) producing CD4⁺ T cells, even at the expense of a higher *H. pylori* load in the gastric mucosa of experimentally infected mice [13]. In another study, it had been suggested that gastritis due to *H. pylori* is associated with loss of immune-regulation and alteration of several cytokines and cell subsets and cannot be attributed to a single immune pathway [14]. Some of *H. pylori*-infected patients have an autoantibody response directed against the H⁺, K⁺- adenosine triphosphatase (ATPase) of gastric parietal cells that correlates with increased atrophy of the corpus

[15]. However, a clear relation of *H. pylori* with gastric autoimmunity is challenging [16].

1.2 AIMS OF STUDY

1. To document the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection among apparently asymptomatic healthy and symptomatic underwent OGD Iraqi people.
2. To correlate the clinical picture of the patients underwent OGD with the type and severity of *H. pylori* infection.
3. To determine how much IgG anti-*H. pylori* serology is predict for the presence of active *H. pylori* infection or the presence of gastroduodenal peptic ulcers (PU).
4. To investigate the prevalence of PCA among symptomatic and asymptomatic *H. pylori* infected Iraqi people as well as to correlate it with type and severity of *H. pylori*-associated diseases.
5. To determine whether there is relation between CD4⁺CD25⁺ T regulatory and IL-17A activities and presence of *H. pylori*-associated gastric autoimmunity.
6. To find out the prevalence of *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains in IgG anti-*H. pylori* positive symptomatic and asymptomatic *H. pylori* infected Iraqi people.
7. To investigate the relationship between the *CagA* strains and the type and severity of *H. pylori* infection as well as with certain host disease markers including the histopathological findings, titer level of IgG anti-*H. pylori* Ab, PCA, IL-17A activity and CD4⁺CD25⁺ T regulatory cell activity in *H. pylori* infected patients.

8. To evaluate the effect of the IgG anti-*H. pylori*, PCA, IL-17A, and Treg levels separately or collectively on the histopathological findings.
9. To compare the alterations of the immune response to *H. pylori* between symptomatic and asymptomatic *H. pylori* infected individuals.

CHAPTER TWO
LITERATURE
REVIEW

2.1 MACROSCOPIC ANATOMY

2.1.1 Stomach (Gaster) (Ventriculus)

The stomach is a j-shaped dilation of the alimentary canal. It is continuous with the oesophagus proximally and with the duodenum distally [17]. Stomach is grossly divided into four parts; the cardia, fundus (upper dome-shaped part), the body (corpus) and the pylorus. Stomach has two openings, cardia and pylorus; two curvatures, greater and lesser; and two surfaces, anterior and posterior (Fig. 2.1) [18].

Figure (2.1): Structure of the stomach and adjacent organs [19].

2.1.2 Duodenum

The duodenum is the shortest, widest, and most fixed part of the small intestine. It is 20-25 centimeter (cm) long. Its course presents a remarkably constant curve, somewhat of the shape of an incomplete circle, which encloses the head of the pancreas [18].

2.2 MICROSCOPIC ANATOMY (Histology)

2.2.1 Stomach

Because fundus and body are identical in microscopic structure, only three histological regions are recognized; cardia, fundus and body, and pylorus. Four layers make up the gastric wall: mucosa, submucosa, muscularispropria and serosa [20] (Fig. 2.2).

Figure (2.2): Structure and walls of the stomach [21].

2.2.1.1 Mucosa

The gastric mucosa consists of a surface epithelium that invaginates to various extents into the lamina propria, forming gastric pits. The lamina propria of the stomach is composed of loose connective tissue interspersed with smooth muscle and lymphoid cells [22].

2.2.1.2 Sub-Mucosa

The sub-mucosa, immediately deep to the mucosa, provides the dense connective tissue skeleton of collagen and elastic fibers. Lymphocytes, plasma cells, arterioles, venules, lymphatics and the sub-mucosal plexus are also contained within sub-mucosa [20].

2.2.1.3 Muscularis Propria

Muscularispropria is a combination of three muscle layers; inner oblique muscle fiber course over the gastric fundus. The middle circular fibers encircle the body of the stomach. The outer longitudinal muscle fibers course primarily along the greater and lesser curvatures of the stomach [17].

2.2.1.4 Serosa

Serosa is a continuation of the visceral peritoneum that covers the whole parts of the stomach [17].

2.2.2 Duodenum

Microscopically, the duodenum differs dramatically from the gastric mucosa with the change from gastric glands and pits to mucosa lined

with villi surrounded by crypts of Lieberkuhn and sub-mucosa with characteristic Brunner's glands [18].

2.3 HELICOBACTER PYLORI

2.3.1 History of *H. pylori*

Spiral bacteria were originally observed in human gastric tissue many years ago [23]. The first human study was done by Doenges (1939) who found the bacteria in 43% of gastric patients, but Doenges could not culture the gastric bacteria. In 1975 Howard Steer published electronmicrographs of spiral bacteria related to gastritis but they could not be cultured [24]. Warren and Marshall in 1982 were the first to culture and identify *H. pylori* (initially called *Campylobacter pyloridis* and then *Campylobacter pylori*) [25]. In 1989, after deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sequencing, the bacterium was not belonging in the *Campylobacter* genus; it was placed in its own genus, *Helicobacter* [26]. The name *pylori* come from the Latin word *pylorus*, which means gate keeper, and refers to the pyloric valve (the circular opening leading from the stomach into the duodenum) [27]. In 1991, several reports had affirm the association between *H. pylori* infection with the presence of gastric cancer [28] and MALT lymphoma of the stomach [29]. In February 1994, the National Institutes of Health published an opinion stating that most recurrent GU were caused by *H. pylori* [30]. In June 1994, International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) Working Group of the World Health Organization (WHO) classified *H. pylori* as group I human carcinogens [29].

2.3.2 Classification of *H. Pylori*

Helicobacter pylori was classified as following:

Order: Campylobacterales, **Family:** Helicobacteraceae, **Subdivision:** Proteobacteria, **Genus:** Helicobacter, and **Species:** pylori [31].

2.3.3 Microbiology of *H. Pylori*

2.3.3.1 Morphology

Helicobacter pylori is a spiral shaped, gram negative rods, it is about 2.5x0.5 micrometer (μm) in size with four to eight unipolar flagella [32] (Fig. 2.3). It is non-sporulating, actively motile with cork screw motion [33]. Under stress, such as prolonged culture, *H. pylori* may lose its morphologic characteristic and first become more simply curved and eventually coccoid [34], these coccoid forms appear to be metabolically active and transmissible but not cultivatable [35].

Figure (2.3): *Helicobacter pylori* electronic image [36].

2.3.3.2 Biochemical Features

A characteristic feature of *H. pylori* is the abundant production of urease [37]. It does not ferment or oxidize carbohydrates and it is oxidase positive and catalase positive which may play a role in virulence. It also produce alkaline phosphatase, glutamine amino peptidase, lucine amino peptidase and deoxyribonuclotidase (DNase) [38 and 39]. Hydrogen sulfide production is variable on lead acetate paper but negative on triple sugar iron agar [40]. In addition it possesses P-type ATPase and expresses two heat shock proteins A and B (HSPA and HSPB) [41].

2.3.3.3 Cultivation and Requirements

Helicobacter pylori is a microaerophilic organism, it need 5% O₂, 10% CO₂ and 85% nitrogen with 98% of humidity. It grows well at 37 centigrade (C°) but not at 42 C° [25 and 42]. The media for primary isolation include, skirrows media (with vancomycin, polymyxine B and trimethoprim), chocolate agar and blood agar (with vancomycin, nalidixic acid and amphotericin) [43]. Growth is slight on Mueller–Hinton agar but increase when supplemented, particularly with lysed horse blood, activated charcoal, starch or isovitalex [44]. The organism does not grow in 1% bile salt, 1% glycine and 3.5% sodium chloride [37]. It grows in 3-6 day when incubated at 37 C°. Colonies are translucent and 1-2 μm in diameter [43].

2.3.4 Epidemiology of *H. pylori*

2.3.4.1 Prevalence of *H. pylori* in Population

Helicobacter pylori colonize more than half of the worlds population, making it the most wide spread infection in the world [45].

The prevalence of *H. pylori* infection has been shown to increase with age, with an estimated (50-60%) of people over 55 years old being infected compared with only (10-20 %) of young adults [46].

2.3.4.2 Mode of Transmission

The infection is acquired by oral ingestion of the bacterium and is mainly transmitted within families in early childhood [47]. Several mechanisms of *H. pylori* transmission involving the feco-oral [48 and 49], oral-oral [50] or gastro-oral route [51] have been proposed.

2.3.5 Risk Factors of *H. pylori* Infection

2.3.5.1 Hypochlorhydria

In vivo experiments support that many exposures do not result in chronic infection, windows of opportunity such as period of hypochlorhydria may exist when the stomach permits infection, in two

human inoculation experiments, infection could not be reestablished without altering the gastric pH with histamine antagonists [25 and 52], because *H. pylori* is not acidophilic and low pH reduce activity of urease and synthesis of nascent urease [53].

2.3.5.2 Blood Group Antigen

Lewis (Le) blood group antigens (Ag) are commonly present in the human gastric mucosa. The Le^b blood group Ag mediates *H. pylori* attachment to human gastric mucosa, therefore gastric tissue lacking Le^b expression did not bind *H. pylori*. In addition, bacteria did not bind to Le^b Ag substituted with a terminal N-acetylgalactosamine α 1-3 residue (Blood group A determinant), suggesting that the availability of *H. pylori* receptors might be reduced in individuals of blood group A and B phenotype as compared with blood group O individuals [54].

2.3.5.3 Age

The progressions of mucosal change from superficial gastritis to PU and carcinoma probably requires decades, therefore individuals who acquire *H. pylori* infection early in life have the highest risk of malignancy and PU when become adult [55].

2.3.5.4 Environmental Factors

Helicobacter pylori infection is most frequently detected in individuals of low socioeconomic status with poor sanitation and hygiene, crowding living condition and poor water supply [56 and 57].

An adequate intake of vitamin C is negatively associated with infection prevalence and total dietary fibers were inversely associated with DU [57].

2.3.5.5 Genetics

Many of the pathogenic effects of *H. pylori* infection are related to chronic active inflammation, which is controlled and maintained by the complex interplay of proinflammatory and anti-inflammatory

mediators such as IL-1 beta (β), IL-8, IL-10, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), myeloperoxidase (MPO) and others. Many genetic polymorphisms that affect the expression levels of these inflammatory mediators have been described [58].

More than 20% of patients had a family history of DU, compared with only 5-10% of control groups. A rare genetic association existed between familial hyper pepsin-ogenemia type I (a genetic phenotype leading to enhanced secretion of pepsin) and DU [45].

2.3.6 Virulence Factors of *H. pylori*

It is well established that only a minority of patients with *H. pylori* infection develop severe inflammation to PU or gastric cancer [59]. Recent evidence suggests, virulence factors alone do not seem crucial in the progression of inflammation towards a more severe disease; rather, other host derived and environmental factors are more significant in determining clinical outcome [45 and 59].

2.3.6.1 Colonization Factors

Colonization factors are attributes of an organism that allow it to establish its presence and to persist despite the host's attempts to rid himself of infection [59].

2.3.6.1.1 Microaerophilic Character

Microaerophilic character of *H. pylori* permits it to colonize and survive within mucus gel [60].

2.3.6.1.2 Flagella and Motility

Flagella allow the bacterium to swim across the viscous gastric mucous and reach the more neutral pH below the mucus [61].

2.3.6.1.3 Urease System

Helicobacter pylori produces large amounts of urease and it has been estimated that up to 10% of the total protein content of *H. pylori* consists of urease [58].

Urease hydrolysis urea to form ammonia and carbon dioxide, and ammonia absorb acid to form ammonium. There are data showing that the organisms do buffer their periplasm that lies between their inner and outer membrane, in acidic pH using intra urease activity [62].

2.3.6.1.4 Adhesins

Helicobacter pylori selectively binds to gastric epithelial cells and its colonization of digestive tract is limited to areas lined by gastric type epithelial cells [63]. Adhesion is necessary for the initiation of the inflammatory cascade, particularly for IL-8 secretion by gastric epithelial cells and promoting more severe disease [64]. There are two types of adhesions in *H. pylori*, the blood group Ag binding adhesion (BabA); binds to Le^b epitopes present on the gastric epithelial cells [65] and the sialic acid binding adhesion (SabA); binds to sialyl-Le^x epitops [66 and 67].

2.3.6.1.5 Induction of Hypochlorhydria

Acute infection with *H. pylori* is accompanied by transient hypochlorhydria [68]. Suggestions for the mechanism by which *H. pylori* increase the gastric pH includes:

1. Presence of acid neutralizing substances (ammonia) in the infected gastric mucosa [69].
2. Increased levels of cytokines, such as IL-1 β , which is known to inhibit gastric acid secretion [69].
3. Exposure of parietal cells to acid inhibitory substances released by *H. pylori* [69].

2.3.6.1.6 P-type Adenosin Triphosphatase (P-type ATPase)

This enzyme catalyzes an NH₄⁺/H⁺ exchange. This activity would prevent excessive alkalization of organism from ammonia i.e. keep pH within about 7 [41].

2.3.6.2 Factors That Allow Organism to Evade Host Defense

Helicobacter pylori possess a well-defined battery of virulence factors that allow it to evade host defense. These are:

1. Arginase: *Helicobacter pylori* prevents nitric oxide production by host cells by producing the enzyme arginase. This enzyme is encoded by the *rocF* gene and competes with nitric oxide synthase 2 for the substrate L-arginine and converts it into urea and L-ornithine, rather than nitric oxide [70].
2. Shedding of surface proteins: It has been shown that after successful colonization some bacteria are killed by host defensive mechanisms resulting in shedding of their surface proteins. These proteins are connected to receptor in the surface of other bacteria and bind cytokines and immunoglobulins. This has been interpreted as an indirect defense mechanism of *H. pylori* to evade host defense [71].
3. Catalase and superoxide dismutase: The action of those enzymes may be arrest respiratory burst by detoxify reactive oxygen species [71 and 72].
4. Reactive lipopolysaccharide (LPS): The LPS O Ag of *H. pylori* isolates often contained Le and ABO blood group Ags, i.e. structures similar to those occurring in the human gastric mucosa [73]. Such similarities suggested that blood group Ags function to camouflage the bacterium from the host immune system, i.e there are mechanisms of “molecular mimicry” between *H. pylori* and the host mucosa [71 and 74].

2.3.6.3 Factors That Induce Tissue Injury

2.3.6.3.1 Urease

Ammonia produced by urease is known to be toxic to eukaryotic cells and may potentiate neutrophil-induced mucosal injury [75].

2.3.6.3.2 Cytotoxin Associated Gene A

Most strains of *H. pylori* possess the Cag pathogenicity island (Cag-PAI), a 37-KDa genomic fragment containing 29 genes [76]. Several genes of these encode components of a predicted type IV secretion apparatus that translocates the 120-KDa protein (*CagA*) into the host cell [77 and 78]. *Helicobacter pylori* strains that contain the Cag-PAI are more virulent and are associated with complication of infection such as PU and gastric cancer [79]. Signaling events induced by *CagA* that alter cellular functions might explain why Cag-PAI-positive isolated is associated with severe gastro-duodenal pathology [77].

2.3.6.3.3 The Vacuolating Cytotoxin A (*VacA*)

The Vacuolating Cytotoxin A a pore-forming toxin, forms pores into lysosomal membranes, increasing anion permeability and generating vacuoles. In addition, *VacA* has been shown to reduce transepithelial resistance by loosening tight junctions. Also, *VacA* inhibits Ag binding by major-histocompatibility-complex class II (MHC II) receptor, a mechanism that can contribute to a down regulation of the host immune response, which has been correlated in mice with increased gastritis and atrophy [80]. A variety of data from cell line models and experimental infections of animals also supported its role in pathogenesis, *VacA* had been suggested to induce apoptosis in epithelial cells *in vitro* [81 and 82] and to have a role in pathogenesis inhibition of T-cell proliferation [81 and 83].

2.3.6.3.4 The Neutrophil Activating Protein of *H. pylori* (Hp-NAP)

Helicobacter pylori-NAP has been shown to be chemotactic for neutrophils and monocytes. It induces the production of oxygen radicals in human neutrophils via a cascade of intracellular activation events that may contribute to the damage of the stomach mucosa [84].

2.3.6.3.5 *IceA* (Induced by Contact with Epithelium Gene A)

IceA is a gene that is induced by contact with epithelium. The gene product is unknown, but it seems to be a bacterial restriction enzyme. There are two variants of *IceA* gene *IceA1* and *IceA2*. A study in Japan showed that the *IceA1* allele was associated with increased gastric inflammation [85].

2.3.6.3.6 Lipopolysaccharide

Lipopolysaccharide stimulate the epithelial cells to produce pro-inflammatory cytokines [86], and activates mononuclear and polymorph nuclear (PMN) cells to produce cytokine, superoxide, TNF- α and other pro-inflammatory molecules [53].

2.3.6.3.7 Surface Binding Protein

Helicobacter pylori surface compounds bind with host proteins such as fetuin, heparin/haparan sulphate, hyaluronic acid and vitronectin, in the presence of complement could allow the bacteria to avoid phagocytosis. This may be very important for persistence of *H. pylori* microorganism on inflammatory gastric mucosa [32].

2.3.6.3.8 Blood Group Antigen Binding Adhesion

Adherence of *H. pylori* is mediated by BabA that is important for gastric inflammation, bacterial colonization and for induction of the IL-8 [87].

2.3.6.3.9 Enzymes (Lipase, Protease and Phospholipase A)

Lipase and protease degrade the mucus layer and phospholipase A disrupts the phospholipids layer in the apical surface of mucus cells [88].

2.3.7 Pathogenesis of *H. pylori*

After being ingested, *H. pylori* has to evade the bactericidal activity of the gastric luminal contents and establish intimate contact with the mucous layer. The enzyme urease metabolizes urea to carbon dioxide

and ammonia to buffer the gastric acid. Flagella allow the bacterium to swim across the viscous gastric mucus and reach the more neutral pH below the mucus [15 and 79]. Once below the mucus, *H. pylori* adheres tightly to the underlying cells. The best characterized adhesin, BabA, is a 78 kDa outer-membrane protein that binds to the fucosylated Le^b blood-group Ag [15].

Rearrangement of genomic DNA allows a variety of pathogens to adapt expression of surface Ags and evade host immunity. *Helicobacter pylori* has the highest rate of genetic recombination of any known bacterial species, suggesting that this process confers a selective advantage in colonization [79].

Approximately 50% of all *H. pylori* strains secrete *VacA*, a highly immunogenic 95-kDa protein that induces massive vacuolization in epithelial cells *in vitro*. The *VacA* protein plays an important role in the pathogenesis of both PU and gastric cancer. The activities of *VacA* include membrane channel formation, disruption of endosomal and lysosomal activity, effects on integrin receptor-induced cell signaling, interference with cytoskeleton-dependent cell functions, induction of apoptosis and immune modulation [58].

Vacuolating Cytotoxin A forms pores in epithelial cell membranes, thus inducing the release of urea and anions from the host cells. It also increases transcellular permeability, leading to the release of nutrients and cations. Interestingly, a significant part of the secreted toxin is not released into the environment but remains associated with the outer membrane of *H. pylori*. Upon bacterial contact with host cells, these toxin clusters are transferred to the host cell surface and exert their toxic action. Although many of the effects of *VacA* are described only for gastric epithelial cells, secreted *VacA* does seem to penetrate into deeper tissues, where it can interact with other relevant cell types such

as granulocytes, monocytes, B cells and T cells. The interaction of *VacA* with these immune cells results in inhibition of Ag presentation and T-cell proliferation [58].

About 60 to 80% of *H. pylori* strains in the world can produce *CagA* [4] which has been identified as a marker of the Cag-PAI [5], a 37-KDa genomic fragment containing 29 genes [76]. Several genes of these encoded proteins serve as building blocks of a type IV secretion apparatus, which forms a syringe like structure capable of penetrating the gastric epithelial cells and facilitating the translocation of *CagA*, peptidoglycan and possibly other bacterial factors into host cells. Once delivered inside the cell, the *CagA* protein is phosphorylated at tyrosine residues in EPIYA motifs by Src family kinases. Phosphorylated *CagA* then interacts with a range of host signaling molecules, such as the tyrosine phosphatase Src homology 2 domain-containing protein (SHP 2), which results in morphological changes in the epithelial cells [58 and 89].

There is considerable variation in the number of the EPIYA tyrosine phosphorylation motifs among the *CagA* proteins of different *H. pylori* isolates. The amount of tyrosine phosphorylation of *CagA* is directly associated with the number of repeats. Strains possessing *CagA* with greater numbers of these repeats induce more pronounced morphological changes in cultured epithelial cells and have been associated with an increased risk of gastric carcinogenesis and might contribute to the Life long colonization of the host [58].

2.3.8 Host Response to *H. Pylori*

2.3.8.1 Primary Immune Response

Toll-like receptors (TLRs) on epithelial cells recognize and react to semiconserved bacterial products. Most gram-negative pathogens, TLR4 mediated recognition of bacterial LPS is a key activator of the

innate immune response in epithelial cells, however, *H. pylori* LPS is a relatively weak inducer. *Helicobacter pylori* LPS does activate nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B), but this is via TLR2 rather than via TLR4. Although TLR4 is involved in the induction of an immune response against *H. pylori*, TLR2 and TLR5, rather than TLR4, seem to be the predominant receptors for *H. pylori* Ag-induced NF- κ B activation and chemokine expression in the cells of the gastric mucosa [58].

The intracellular peptidoglycan, transferred into the cytoplasm by Cag-PAI-mediated contact between the epithelial cell and the bacterium, may be a key activator of the innate response against *H. pylori*. This intracellular peptidoglycan is recognized by nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain protein 1 (Nod1), a member of the recently discovered Nod family. Two members of this protein family, Nod1 (also known as CARD4) and Nod2 (CARD15), are involved in the recognition of bacterial peptidoglycans and seem to act as intracellular (Nod1) and extracellular (Nod2) receptors for gram-negative bacteria in epithelial cells [58].

Bacterial contact with monocytes and other antigen-presenting cells (APCs) via TLRs leads to the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-8. *Helicobacter pylori* infection has been shown to be associated with increased levels of these cytokines which, in turn, act as local chemo-attractants, inducing granulocytic infiltration [90]. Several studies have demonstrated that contact between *H. pylori* and gastric epithelial cells results in a rapid activation of NF- κ B, which is followed by increased IL-8 expression [91]. In addition to NF- κ B, mitogen activated protein kinases (MAPKs) have been implicated as mediators of *H. pylori* induced IL-8 expression. *In vitro* studies utilizing IL-8 reporter constructs have now revealed that *H. pylori*-induced IL-8 gene expression is dependent

upon activation of both NF- κ B and the early-response transcription factor activator protein1 (AP-1), (via activation of MAPKs), indicating that synergistic interactions between AP-1 and NF- κ B within the IL-8 promoter are required for maximal *H. pylori*-induced IL-8 production [92].

2.3.8.2 Cellular Response

The inflammatory response initially consists of neutrophils, followed by lymphocytes (T- and B-cells), plasma cells and macrophages, along with varying degrees of epithelial cell degeneration and injury [79].

Since *H. pylori* rarely, if ever, invades the gastric mucosa, the host response is triggered primarily by the attachment of bacteria to epithelial cells. The pathogen can bind to class II MHC molecules on the surface of gastric epithelial cells, inducing their apoptosis [93]. The organism produces a number of antigenic substances, including HSP, urease and LPS, all of which can be taken up and processed by lamina propria macrophages and activate T-cells. Cellular disruption, especially adjacent to epithelial tight junctions, undoubtedly enhances Ag presentation to the lamina propria and facilitates immune stimulation. The net result is increased production of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1, IL-6 and TNF- α , and most notably, IL-8 [79].

Helicobacter pylori strains carrying the Cag-PAI induce a far stronger IL-8 response than Cag negative strains and this response depends on activation of NF- κ B and the early-response transcription factor AP-1. During specific immune responses, different subgroups of T cells emerge. These cells participate in mucosal protection and help distinguish pathogenic bacteria from commensals. Immature Th 0 cells expressing CD4 can differentiate into two functional subtypes: Th1 cells, secreting IL-2 and IFN- γ , and Th2 cells, secreting IL-4, IL-5 and IL-10. T helper 2 cells stimulate B cells in response to

extracellular pathogens, while Th1 cells are induced mostly in response to intracellular pathogens. Because *H. pylori* is non invasive and induces a strong humoral response, a Th2-cell response would be expected. Paradoxically, *H. pylori*-specific gastric mucosal T cells generally present a Th1 phenotype. Studies in gene-targeted mice have further showed that Th1 cytokines promote gastritis, whereas Th2 cytokines are protective against gastric inflammation. This Th1 orientation may be due to increased antral production of IL-18 in response to *H. pylori* infection. This biased Th1 response, combined with Fas-mediated apoptosis of *H. pylori*-specific T-cell clones, may favor the persistence of *H. pylori* [15]. A Th1-predominant immune response is associated with elevated levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-12, IL-18 and TNF- α . The host genetic background contributes to the immune and inflammatory response to *H. pylori* infection. The IL-1B gene encodes the expression of IL-1 β , a potent pro-inflammatory cytokine and powerful inhibitor of gastric acid secretion that plays a major role in initiating and amplifying the inflammatory response to *H. pylori* infection [79].

The role of CD8⁺ T cells in the gastric mucosa of *H. pylori*-infected individuals is less clear than that of the CD4⁺ T cells. Although their numbers are also increased, the CD8⁺ T cells that are found in the infected tissue are thought to be intraepithelial lymphocytes. Their contribution to the local response is in the form of IFN- γ production, which in turn helps increase class II MHC molecule expression on adjacent cells [94].

2.3.8.2.1 Interleukin-17A

Recently, a novel and unique subset of IL-17-producing Th17 cells, distinct from Th1 and Th2 cells, has been discovered [95]. The Th1 cell subset protects the host against intracellular bacteria, while

proinflammatory Th17 cells are involved in the protection against extracellular bacteria. The development of Th17 cells in human beings depends on a cytokine milieu rich in IL-1 β , IL-6 and transforming growth factor β (TGF- β) that initiates the differentiation process and IL-23 that participates in the expansion and maintenance of the Th17 cells [96].

More recently, it was found that IL-17 has 6 family members (IL-17A–F), and IL-17A is the prototypic IL-17 family member, also called simply IL-17. Interleukin-17A is recognized in multiple studies as a proinflammatory cytokine which induces severe inflammation with infiltration of neutrophils, but a few reports have indicated anti-inflammatory effects of IL-17A on *H. pylori*-induced gastritis [95].

2.3.8.3 Humoral Response

Nearly everyone infected with *H. pylori* develops specific Abs, which are found in serum and in gastric aspirates or extracts of stomach. Accordingly, elevated titers of IgG and IgA Abs directed against membrane proteins (MP), flagelin, urease, LPS and *H. pylori* adhesin A (HpaA) have been reported in patients infected with *H. pylori* [97]. *Helicobacter pylori* strains are susceptible to complement and activate it either via the classical pathway, even in the absence of specific Abs, (the mechanism for this phenomenon is not known but could be secondary to activation of complement via low levels of anti-endotoxin Abs), or by the alternative pathway. Despite this vigorous immune response, *H. pylori* is not eradicated unless an infected individual is treated with a combination of antibiotics and lifelong chronic infection usually develops. These observations suggest that gastric mucus may be a protective niche in which *H. pylori* exist and are relatively inaccessible to specific Abs or their effector functions.

The ineffective humoral response generated towards *H. pylori* and its components may actually contribute to pathogenesis [79 and 98].

It had been shown that human serum from both infected and non-infected subjects exerted a bactericidal effect on *H. pylori*. Furthermore heat inactivation abolished the killing effect of the serum samples on the organism, strongly suggesting that it was complement mediated. Later it was reported that bovine normal serum and serum from immunized cows is highly bactericidal for *H. pylori*. This bactericidal effect is destroyed by heating to 56 C° for 30 minutes (min) and restored by the addition of fetal calf serum as a source of complement, indicating that the bactericidal effect is probably dependent on an Ab–complement system. However, the bactericidal activity did not correlate with titres of specific Ab or with IgG concentrations. The serum samples from infected subjects killed the organism more effectively than serum from non-infected individuals, indicating that some of this effect is mediated by the classical pathway [79].

Sampling of gastric secretions from *H. pylori*-infected individuals also reveals an active mucosal Ab response, primarily of the IgA isotype. This response is consistent with the predominance of secretory IgA (sIgA) in the gastric secretions of healthy individuals. Secretory IgA anti-*H. pylori* Abs are also found in saliva and breast milk. Studies have shown that sIgA can interfere with the ability of some enteric pathogens to establish infection. Others have shown that sIgA can inhibit bacterial adherence. However, the systemic Ab response and the sIgA response against *H. pylori* do not inhibit the organism from adhering to gastric cells *in vitro*. This may explain why chronic infection develops in infected subjects despite a vigorous immune response [79].

2.3.8.3.1 Anti-*CagA* Antibodies

Cytotoxin associated gene A is a very immunogenic protein and serum Abs against *CagA* Ag can be used to *CagA* expression by *H. pylori*. Serum IgG Abs against *CagA* Ag may be a reliable marker of carriage of a *CagA*⁺ *H. pylori* strain [99 and 100].

2.3.8.3.2 Parietal Cells Autoantibodies

Parietal cells in the corpus secrete gastric acid via the proton pump, i.e., the gastric H⁺, K⁺-ATPase, which is found in the apical secretory canaliculi [101].

Some studies suggested molecular mimicry between epitopes on *H. pylori* and Le blood group Ags expressed on gastric epithelial cell [102]. It is possible however, that apart from this hypothesis other autoimmune mechanisms are responsible for the generation of antigastric autoantibodies. Since almost no immunological surveillance exists in the normal gastric mucosa, one can describe this region as an immunologically privileged site, which loses its virginal status by colonization with *H. pylori*, leading to expression of MHC class II Ags on gastric epithelial cells and aggregation of a dense lymphoplasma cellular infiltrate within the gastric mucosa [102]. Presentation by epithelial cells of gastric H⁺, K⁺-ATPase to CD4⁺ H⁺, K⁺-ATPase β subunit-specific T cells that have escaped negative selection in the thymus may result in T-cell activation and proliferation, in which these autoreactive T cells could provide help for B-cell stimulation and autoantibody production [103 and 104]. At least 11 epitopes of human H⁺, K⁺-ATPase recognized by autoreactive T cells have been identified [105].

2.3.8.4 Regulatory T Cell-Immune Regulation

2.3.8.4.1 History of Regulatory T Cells

A study conducted in 1995 demonstrated that mouse T cells with suppressor activity was confined to a minor subset of T cells that constitutively expressed the IL-2 receptor α subunit (IL-2R α) which is also known as CD25. These cells are CD4⁺CD25⁺ which were termed as regulatory T cell or Treg [106].

T regulatory cells are now categorized into two main classes; naturally occurring Treg (nTreg), which develop their regulatory function in the thymus and the Tregs cells that up-regulate their regulatory function in the periphery or *in vitro* during various experimental conditions, *i.e.* induced Treg (iTreg) [106].

Expression of the IL-2R α chain (CD25) is one of the most extensively used markers for the isolation and characterization of Treg both in mice and humans [106].

2.3.8.4.2 Suppressive Mechanisms Used by Regulatory T Cells

1. Inhibitory Cytokines: The inhibitory cytokines most important for Treg suppression are IL-10 and TGF- β [106].
2. Cytolysis: Suppression by cytolysis is suggested to be carried out by granzyme A, granzyme B and perforin. In human this has been shown on *in vitro* stimulated peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC). However, gastric mucosal CD4⁺CD25⁺T cells isolated from tumor and tumor-free mucosa do not express granzyme A, granzyme B or perforin. It has also been suggested that Treg may use two other cytotoxic mechanisms; the tumor-necrosis-factor-related apoptosis-inducing ligand-death receptor 5 (TRAIL-DR5) pathway and galectin-1 [106].
3. Metabolic Disruption: The high expression of CD25 (IL-2R α) empowers Treg cell to “consume” IL-2 and therefore starve

actively dividing effector T cells by depleting the IL-2 they need to survive. The coordinated expression of CD39/CD73 on Treg which generate the inhibitory molecule adenosine can suppress effector T cells by binding to their A_{2A} receptor. Regulatory T cell can also use cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) to suppress effector T cells by transfer through membrane gap junctions [106].

4. Modulation of Dendritic Cells (DCs): Regulatory T cells down-modulate B7-molecules on DCs in a cytotoxic T-lymphocyte Ag-4 (CTLA-4)-dependent way, thereby enhancing suppression of T-cell activity. Regulatory T cells can also in a CTLA-4-dependent way induce up-regulation of indoleamine 2, 3-dioxygenase (IDO) in DC, resulting in a suppression of effector T cells. Indoleamine 2, 3-dioxygenase catalyses the degradation of tryptophan, generating suppressive metabolites, which can anergize T cells or even induce the differentiation of new Tregs. Neuropilin-1 which is expressed mostly by Treg but not naïve T cells, promote prolonged interaction with immature DC (iDC). This will give Treg an advantage over naïve T cells in modulating the function of DCs [106].

2.3.8.4.3 The Role of Treg During *H. pylori* Infection

Central to an efficient adaptive immune response is the ability to tightly regulate immune activation to prevent responses to self-Ags, permit responses to foreign Ags and limit collateral damage [107].

Regulatory T cells, especially naturally arising CD4⁺CD25⁺ Tregs, actively engaged in the maintenance of immunological self-tolerance and immune homeostasis [108].

Recent evidence suggests that the activation of Treg might result in decreased pathological response and prolong persistence of infection as a mechanism for the maintenance of pathogen specific immunologic

memory [109]. In one previous study, it was demonstrated that *H. pylori* infection can decrease T cell response as well as induce T cell anergy, and memory T cells isolated from peripheral blood (PB) from *H. pylori*-infected people responded less to stimulation with *H. pylori* Ags than cells isolated from non-infected subjects due to the presence of Treg cells (CD4⁺CD25⁺) in the PB of *H. pylori*-infected individuals which could inhibit the response of CD4⁺ T cells to *H. pylori*. Hence, these observations may help explain the inability of the host response to eliminate the infection due to the activation of Treg cells, indicating that *H. pylori* infection results in downregulation of the immune response through interaction with Treg cells [97].

2.3.9 Clinical Feature of *H. pylori* Colonization

2.3.9.1 Asymptomatic Infection

In most patients (80%), *H. pylori* does not cause clinical symptoms and the infection can persist for a lifetime without further problems [110].

2.3.9.2 Non-Ulcer Dyspepsia

The role of *H. pylori* infection in dyspepsia not associated with ulcer remains controversial. In some studies, seropositive of patient with *H. pylori* in dyspeptic patients was 71%, other study yielded a mean prevalence of 65% [32].

2.3.9.3 Chronic Abdominal Pain

When infection associated with chronic gastritis (CG) alone, the only symptom may be recurrent abdominal pain [111].

2.3.10 *Helicobacter pylori* Infection Types

2.3.10.1 Gastritis (inflammation of gastric mucosa)

Clinicians, endoscopists and pathologists have different concepts of what gastritis is. Some think of it as a symptom complex, others as a description of the endoscopic appearance of the stomach, and still

others use the term to describe microscopic inflammation of the stomach [112].

2.3.10.1.1 Classification of Gastritis

There was no universally accepted classification of gastritis. The Sydney system was an attempt to unify terminology for endoscopic and histological gastritis. The system was updated in 1996 into a scheme that combine topological, morphological and etiological information. The Sydney system was a histologic division of gastritis, it recognized three morphological patterns: acute gastritis, chronic gastritis and special forms each had a standard grading scale include: mild, moderate and marked. The graded variables were degree of chronic inflammatory infiltrate (lymphocytes and plasma cells), density of *H. pylori* colonization, superficial epithelial damage, degree of inflammatory activity (neutrophils) and degree of intestinal metaplasia (IM). Failure to obtain adequate numbers of biopsies from various regions of the stomach often prevents accurate classification and often precludes a thorough assessment of the distribution of gastritis [2 and 113].

- **Acute Gastritis:**

Initial colonization by *H. pylori* results in an acute inflammatory response (acute gastritis), which was characterized by infiltration by lymphocytes and neutrophils into the gastric mucosa [114]. The acute phase of colonization with *H. pylori* may be associated with transient nonspecific symptoms, such as fullness, nausea and vomiting, and with considerable inflammation of both the proximal and distal stomach mucosa, and pangastritis. This phase is often associated with hypochlorhydria, which can last for months. It is unclear whether this initial colonization can be followed by spontaneous clearance and resolution of gastritis, and if so, how often this occurs [58].

- **Chronic Gastritis:**

Initial colonization by *H. pylori* results in an acute inflammatory response, but if this initial response failed to clear the infection, there is a gradual accumulation of neutrophils, T cells, B cells and macrophages into the gastric mucosa. After a few weeks, there is a massive invasion of the tissue by immune and inflammatory cells, which is a characteristic histological picture of chronic active gastritis. The continuous presence of *H. pylori* elicits a local mucosal IgA Ab response and a systemic humoral response, neither of which could eradicate the infection [114]. Chronic *H. pylori* gastritis is the most common type of diffuse gastritis although it began as an antral–predominant gastritis progression to the body, fundus and cardia of the stomach over many decades. In the early stages, the inflammatory process and histological changes were superficial. However, the inflammation extended to the deep glands and intraglandular area, causing progressive loss of glandular mass (atrophy). Frequently, the surface epithelium undergoes IM. When *H. pylori* gastritis was associated with large and friable lesions, there is always concern about dysplastic change or frank carcinoma in the IM [115].

- **Atrophic Gastritis:**

Atrophic gastritis was defined as a gradual loss of gastric glandular tissue as a consequence of long-term mucosal damage, in particular due to chronic inflammation. In fact, the tissue destruction might involve progressive loss of all specialized mucosal cells including the acid producing parietal cells, pepsinogen producing chief cells and mucus producing gland. When these cell types had diminished, the protective mucus layer would gradually disappeared and the acid secretion would cease. Such pathological changes increased the risk of gastric ulceration and development of gastric adenocarcinoma, but

somewhat contradictory, they were found protective against DU because acid secretion is lowered (Fig. 2.4) [69].

2.3.10.2 Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD)

The term "peptic ulcer" is commonly used to refer to ulcerations of the stomach, duodenum, or both; but PU can develop in any portion of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) that is exposed to acid and pepsin in sufficient concentration and duration. Ulcers are defined histologically as a breach in the mucosa of the alimentary tract that extends through musculis mucosa into the submucosa or deeper; whereas more superficial necrotic defects are considered erosions [2].

2.3.10.2.1 Pathogenesis of Peptic Ulcers

Ulceration could follow either destruction or removal of the mucus barrier, or a loss of integrity of the surface epithelium. Epithelial injury as a consequence of *H. pylori* infection either produced directly by cytokines and ammonia, or indirectly, as a result of the inflammatory reaction. Ulcer development in the presence of *H. pylori* is influenced by a variety of host and bacterial factors. Ulcers mostly occur at sites where mucosal inflammation is most severe. In subjects with decreased acid output, this usually is the gastric transitional zone between corpus and antrum, giving rise to GU disease (Fig. 2.4). The acid output in GU patients had been found to be below normal levels, but slow gastric motility and slow gastric emptying may predispose a person to GU. Gastric ulcers were most found distal to the junction between the antrum and the acid secretory mucosa, and were quite rare in the gastric fundus [58 and 115]. If acid production is normal to high, the most severe inflammation usually is found in the distal stomach and proximal duodenum, giving rise to juxta-pyloric and DU disease (Fig. 2.4) [58]. Rapid gastric emptying or impaired mucosal defense from smoking or inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis, play a

role in DU formation. However; that chronic antral gastritis that occurs with *H. pylori*, in addition to the high acid output, leads to duodenitis and eventually to DU. Duodenal ulcers occurs most often in the first portion of the duodenum (>95%), with about 90% located within the 3cm of the pylorus [115].

Pattern of gastritis	Gastric histology	Duodenal histology	Acid secretion	Clinical condition
<p>Pan-gastritis</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronic inflammation • Atrophy • Intestinal metaplasia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Normal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gastric ulcer • Gastric cancer
<p>Antral-predominant</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chronic inflammation • Polymorph activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gastric metaplasia • Active chronic inflammation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duodenal ulcer

Figure (2.4): Acid secretion and the associated pattern of gastritis play an important role in disease outcome in *H. pylori* infection [58].

2.3.10.3 Intestinal Metaplasia

Intestinal metaplasia involved transformation of gastric epithelial cells into goblet cells. These changes appear most often as a consequence of continuous regeneration of tissue and abnormal stimulation of growth during chronic inflammation. Both atrophic gastritis and IM occurred during long-term of *H. pylori* infection and both were considered to be risk factors for development of cancer [114].

2.3.10.4 Gastric Cancer

Helicobacter pylori-induced gastritis is characterized by the enhanced production of a variety of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the gastric mucosa which are suggested to play important roles in cancer development. Interleukin-1 β gene polymorphism is reported to be associated with a increased risk factor of gastric cancer in *H. pylori* infection [116]. Other cytokines as TNF α , IL-6, IL-7 and IL-8 may

also play a role in the development of gastric cancer through their enhancement to NF- κ B factor activation which by its role enhances cyclo-oxygenase-2 production that increase the risk of development of gastric cancer in the gastric mucosa [116 and 117]. On the other hand, *H. pylori* CagA-PAI toxin that are injected inside the epithelial cell can induce the hummingbird phenomenon which is a characteristic of an extremely elongated cell shape. Furthermore, CagA has been shown to impair cell-cell adhesion by disturbing tight junctions and causing a loss of cell polarity by inhibiting the PAR1/MARK polarity-regulating kinase. All above mentioned effects of CagA virulence factor of *H. pylori*, plus its role in the destabilization of E-cadherin- β -catenin complex with the resulting activation of β -catenin signal may contribute to gastric cancer development by providing epithelial cell with a suitable environment for neoplastic transformation [116 and 118].

In 50% of gastric cancer, TP53 gene mutation was present. The effect of *H. pylori* if it is direct or indirect in the induction of such mutation is unknown. However, there are a piece of evidence that *H. pylori* may directly induces gene mutation by enhancing the expression of cytidine deaminase in gastric mucosal cells which is essential for somatic hypermutation and class switch recombination of immunoglobulin genes in B lymphocytes [116]. Finally, the effect of *H. pylori* in DNA methylation of gastric mucosa was discussed. Such methylation may participate in gastric carcinogenesis through silencing tumor suppressor genes [116].

2.3.10.5 Gastric Lymphoma (MALT)

Strong link has been documented between *H. pylori* infection and development of the MALT lymphoma. The frequency of MALT lymphoma was found to be 3 to 6 time higher in *H. pylori* infected

individuals as compared to controls. Treatment and eradication of *H. pylori* can result in regression of malignancy in up to 75% of cases [32].

2.3.10.6 Gasrto-Oesophageal Reflux Disease (GORD)

The interaction between *H. pylori*, GORD and treatment with antisecretory drugs is extremely complex and highly contentious. Epidemiological studies have shown that the prevalence of *H. pylori* infection is no higher in patients with GORD than in healthy controls matched for age and sex. Indeed, *H. pylori* infection may be less common in patients with GORD, particularly those with more severe (erosive) disease, suggesting that the bacterium may have a protective role, perhaps by producing corpus gastritis and thus decreasing the output of acid [32].

2.3.11 Diagnosis of *H. pylori* Infection

There are many different testing strategies for *H. pylori* infection. It has become standard to classify these as endoscopic and non-endoscopic [2].

2.3.11.1 Endoscopic (invasive) Tests

2.3.11.1.1 Endoscopy

Recent studies highlighted that the presence of *H. pylori* could be assessed on the basis of the macroscopic patterns, but it is still unknown how macroscopic findings are related to histomorphological changes and the presence of *H. pylori* in the gastric mucosa [119]. Until recently, the endoscopic features of *H. pylori*-induced gastritis and *H. pylori*-negative normal mucosa were unknown. Some articles reported that endoscopic features were not sensitive indicators in the diagnosis of histological gastritis caused by *H. pylori* [120].

Gastric biopsy specimen obtained during endoscopy can be used for detection of *H. pylori* infection and even isolation of the organism

through application of some tests as (histological study, culture, biopsy urease test, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) or in situ hybridization) [36].

2.3.11.1.2 Biopsy Urease Test

Although many different bacteria are urease positive, *H. pylori* has the highest urease activity known and the only species likely to survive the otherwise hostile intragastric environment. Therefore; the demonstration of urease activity directly in a biopsy taken from the gastric mucosa is a reliable indicator of active *H. pylori* infection [36].

2.3.11.1.3 Histology

Histology has long been considered the “gold standard” in *H. pylori* diagnosis. However, the results of histology are dependent on the experience of the pathologist, the number of biopsies taken, the use of special stains and the density of *H. pylori* in the gastric mucosa. In clinical practice, two biopsies both from the antrum and the corpus are recommended. However, the recommendation of the updated Sydney system to take one extra biopsy, from the incisura angularis gives very little additional information [121]. The organism can be readily recognized by its characteristic curved or S-shaped morphology and its location on the epithelial cell surface, within the gastric pits or in the mucus overlaying the cell surface [122]. However, although histology has its restrictions and is considered expensive, the major advantage of using it is the assessment of morphological changes of the gastric mucosa [121]. The superior advantage of histology is that it demonstrates the presence and severity (grade) of gastritis [2 and 36]. Most infection can be detected with haematoxylin and eosin (H. and E.) stains of gastric tissue, but special stain like Giemsa can be used if H. and E. results are not exclusive. Histological detection of organism has sensitivity at 80-95% with 100% specificity but it is expensive

[32]. The demonstration of acute and chronic inflammatory cells within the gastric mucosa, particularly if in association with lymphoid follicles, is often sufficient to establish the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection, even if the actual organism is not clearly seen [2 and 36].

2.3.11.1.4 Culture

Culture of *H. pylori* from gastric mucosal biopsies is seldom performed in clinical practice and is usually unnecessary. Culture is a demanding technique because of the fastidious, microaerophilic nature of the organism [36]. Biopsy specimens may be cultured for *H. pylori* on antibiotic-containing media (to diminish overgrowth by any competing flora) such as Skirrows medium, as well as with a non-selective medium such as chocolate agar. Plates should be incubated for 2-5 days at 35 C° in a moist microaerobic atmosphere (with 5% oxygen). Coma or S-shaped motile organism with catalase, oxidase and urease activity may be identified as *H. pylori* culture [32].

2.3.11.1.5 Polymerase Chain Reaction Diagnosis

Polymerase chain reaction offers great promise as highly sensitive and specific technique for the detection of *H. pylori* in gastric biopsy specimens which have been described by a number of laboratories. A potential advantage of PCR is that it may enable the diagnosis of *H. pylori* to be made also non-invasively by detecting *H. pylori* DNA in non-gastric fluid such as saliva [36].

2.3.11.2 Non-Endoscopic (non-invasive) Tests

These are used for diagnosis of *H. pylori* status especially after treatment. Non-invasive tests detect the overall presence of *H. pylori* in the gastric cavity, even then the bacteria are irregularly distributed. These methods are less costly and entail less risk and discomfort for the patient, so that they represent the first choice when the added information provided by endoscopy is not necessarily required [123].

2.3.11.2.1 Serological Tests

Infection by *H. pylori* induces local and systemic Abs response. The typical pattern is that of a transient increase of IgM followed by an increase of IgA and IgG levels that persists throughout the infection. These Abs may be detected by enzyme-linked immune-sorbent assay (ELISA) or using latex agglutination methods. The assessed sample is usually serum, and the specific IgG is measured. Immunoglobulin A assessment may be used as a second-line test when a sensitive and well-validated IgG test has produced a negative result. The commercially available IgG-ELISA methods have 90-95% sensitivity and 80-90% specificity. Enzyme-linked immune-sorbent assay is relatively inexpensive and easy to implement in the clinical setting, many tests are available for use to test whole blood, plasma or serum. Commercial enzyme immunoassays (EIA) detecting anti-*H. pylori* serum IgG are the tests of choice, as well as several serological techniques have been used for the study of *H. pylori* infection (e.g. immunochromatographic, complement fixation, passive haemagglutination and immunoblot techniques) [122 and 123].

In epidemiological studies, serological tests offered high sensitivity and specificity and serum assaying of anti-*H. Pylori* IgG Abs could be used as a marker for *H. pylori* infection [124]. Some studies showed that cancer sera provided stronger immunoreactivity while the sera from ulcer patients have more anti-*H. pylori* Abs than sera from gastritis patients [97].

2.3.11.2.2 Urea Breath Test

To perform this test, the patient ingests a small quantity of urea in which the carbon is labeled with either C^{13} or C^{14} . If *H. pylori* is present in the stomach, the labeled urea is hydrolyzed by urease enzyme into ammonia and labeled carbon dioxide. Using mass

spectroscopy C¹³ or scintillography C¹⁴, labeled carbon dioxide is then measured in air exhaled air-over; urea breath test is the best method for detection of an active *H. pylori* infection [123].

2.3.11.2.3 Stool Test

The presence of *H. pylori* in the stools of infected patients led to the development of fecal Ag assay. The stool assay is used to detect specific *H. Pylori* Ag by commercially available EIA. It is an easy and a reliable test with sensitivity and specificity reaching 94% and 91.8% respectively [123].

2.3.12 Treatment and Prevention

The standard first-line therapy is a one week triple therapy consisting of a proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) such as Omeprazole and the antibiotics Clarithromycin and Amoxicillin. For the treatment of Clarithromycin-resistant strains of *H. pylori*, the use of Levofloxacin as part of the therapy has been suggested [36].

Rising antimicrobial resistance increases the need for a prevention strategy for the bacteria. An intramuscular vaccine against *H. pylori* infection is undergoing Phase I clinical trials and has shown an Ab response against the bacterium. However, its clinical usefulness requires further studies [36].

CHAPTER THREE
MATERIALS AND
METHODS

3.1 EQUIPMENT, CHEMICALS, STAINS, KITS AND REAGENTS

3.1.1 Equipment

3.1.1.1 General Laboratory Equipment

Equipment	Manufacturing Company	Country
Tourniquet	-	-
Digital Timer	-	China
Marker Pens	-	China
Writing Board	-	-
Micropipette: 200 microliter(μ l),1000 μ l	Slamed	Germany
Multi-Channel Pipette	Slamed	Germany
Test Tubes Racks	-	China
Eppendorf Tubes Racks	-	Hen Kari
Staining Racks	-	-
Cool Box	-	-
Refrigerator	Beko	Turkey
Freezer	Ishtar	Iraq
Centrifuge	Hettich	Germany
Cylinders: 100 ml, 250 ml	HBG	Germany
Beakers: 100 ml, 250 ml	HBG	Germany
Flask: 500 ml, 1000 ml	HBG	Germany
Sensitive Balance	Precisa	Switzerland
Ordinary Balance	-	-
Water Distiller	Gallen Kump	England
Incubator	Memmert	Germany
Light Microscope	Human	Germany
Flow Cytometry (C4BE6)	Partec	Germany
Endoscopy and Forceps	Olympus	Japan
Water Bath	Histo-line	England
Microtome	Lice Unit	Germany
Automatic Slide Steiner	Lice Unit	Germany

Hot Air Oven (60° C)	Memmert	Germany
Microtiter Plate Washer	Biokit	Germany
Microtiter Plate Reader	Biokit	Germany
Shaker	KAHN	Japan
Blood Sample's Shaker	Karl CloB	Germany

3.1.1.2 Disposable Laboratory Equipment

Equipment	Manufacturing Company	Country
Syringes, sterile:10 ml	Medeco	Belgium
Cotton	Kardelen	Turkey
EDTA Tubes: 3ml	Human	Germany
Vacuum Tubes: 5ml	-	China
Test Tube for Flow Cytometry	Partec	Germany
Gloves	-	Malaysia
Filter Paper	Whatmann	England
Eppendorf Tubes: 500µl,1.5 ml	Citotest	China
Pipette Tips	-	China
Plain Tubes	AFNA	Jordan
Disposable knives	Sigma	Germany
Ordinary Slides	Sail Brand	China
Cover Slips for Histology	Fluka	Germany
Applicator Sticks	-	China

3.1.2 Chemicals, Stains and Reagents

Materials	Manufacturing Company	Country
Ethanol Alcohol (70%)	Media	Syria
40% Formalin	Fluka	Germany
Sodium Di-hydrogen Phosphate (monobasic)	Fluka	Germany
Sodium Phosphate Dibasic	Fluka	Germany

(anhydrous)		
Distilled Water	-	-
Absolute Ethanol (99.9%)	Redel de-Häne	Germany
Xylene	Fluka	Germany
Paraffin Wax	Fluka	Germany
Haematoxylin	BDH	England
Eosin Yelloeish	BDH	England
Disteren Plasticizer Xylene	Sigma	Germany
Hydrochloric Acid	BDH	England

3.1.3 Kits

Kits	Manufacturing Company	Country
<i>OnSite H. pylori</i> Ab Combo Rapid Test	CTK Biotech, Inc.	USA
<i>Helicobacter pylori</i> IgG ELISA Kit	Demeditec	Germany
Cytotoxin Associated Gene A (<i>CagA</i>) Ab (IgG) ELISA Kit	Cusabio	China
Parietal Cell Ab ELISA Kit	Demeditec	Germany
Human Interleukin 17A(IL-17A/IL-17) ELISA Kit	Cusabio	China
Mouse Anti-human CD4 (FITC), CD25 (PE), Dual Color	USBiological	USA
Erythrocyte Lysing Reagent Kit For Wash and no Wash Procedures	Partec	Germany

3.2 STUDY GROUPS

3.2.1 Patients Group

3.2.1.1 Setting

Patients were selected from those attending the Endoscopic Unit at "Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital/Baghdad Medical City", during the period between September 2012 and February 2013.

3.2.1.2 Exclusion Criteria

Patients with the following criteria were excluded from the current study:

1. Under antibiotic therapy for the last 2 weeks.
2. Under non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) for the last 7 days.
3. Under corticosteroidal therapy for the last 4 weeks.
4. Under biological agents therapy currently or previously.
5. Have a blood transfusion during the last 6 months.
6. Have a surgery during the last 6 months.
7. Have a chronic or autoimmune disease.

3.2.1.3 Patient's Partitions

A total of 60 patients (40 males and 20 females) were involved in this study after exclusion criteria. They were all suffering from clinical manifestation of gastro-duodenal ulcer and/or gastritis. Their age range from 18–80 years.

3.2.1.4 Base-line Data Collection

Data were collected through direct interview with the patient and by seeking his/her hospital record as well as previous medical reports (a copy of the questionnaire data sheet is provided in appendix A). Patient's claims were followed as an alternative source of information when his/her previous medical reports were not available. A written

consent was obtained from each patient participating in this study to fulfill the international research ethical criteria.

3.2.2 Negative Control Group

A total of 30 apparently healthy individuals (18 males and 12 females) with an age range of 18-65 years were included in the study. The same exclusion criteria of the patient's group is to be followed for this group, and in addition, subjects with even simple infection were also excluded. All subjects of this group have no gastrointestinal illness of any type.

3.3 STUDY PROTOCOL

The test procedures had been executed in Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital/Baghdad Medical City, Teaching Laboratories/Baghdad Medical City, and Specialist Laboratory center/Baghdad (see Fig. 3.1).

1. Patient's data collection by written questionnaire form and direct interviewing.
2. Samples collections:
 - a. In site sampling for Endoscopy findings* .
 - b. Biopsy samples for histopathology findings* .
 - c. Whole blood samples for blood Treg cell count.
 - d. Serum samples for serological markers.
 - e. Transportation and storage of samples.
3. Samples assessment tests:
 - a. Endoscopic findings for *H. pylori*-associated and-non-associated gastro-enteropathy* .
 - b. Testing the biopsies for *H. pylori*-associated and-non-associated for gastro-enteropathy histological findings* .

*= These tests were done for patients group only.

- c. Testing the whole blood samples for Treg (CD4⁺CD25⁺) cell count by flow cytometry (FC).
- d. Testing the serum samples for serological findings of the following parameters:
 - i. Onsite *H. pylori* Ab combo rapid test.
 - ii. Anti-*H. Pylori* Ab (IgG) assay.
 - iii. Anti-*CagA* Ab (IgG) assay.
 - iv. Anti-parietal cell Ab (IgG) assay.
 - v. Interleukin-17A level assay.
4. Tabulation of all tests results.
5. Statistical analysis for any correlational inter-relationships of all tested parameters.

3.3.1 Samples Collection

3.3.1.1 Endoscopy and Biopsies

Endoscopic examination was conducted in Endoscopic Unit of Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital/Baghdad Medical City. Patients were fasted for at least 8 hours (hrs) before endoscopic examination. All patients were subjected to diagnostic OGD for upper abdominal complaints. Endoscopic examination was performed under local pharyngeal anesthesia. After endoscopic diagnosis; 2-4 mucosal pinch biopsy specimens were taken via sterile standard biopsy forceps.

In all cases; gastric biopsy samples were taken from both antrum (greater and/or lesser curvature), from the incisura and gastric body, as these are the typical recommended sites for *H. pylori* diagnosis [112]. Biopsies specimens were fixed with 10% neutral buffered formalin (NBF) for preparation of paraffin embedded tissue blocks.

**=Neutral buffered formalin.

Figure (3.1): Study protocol

3.3.1.2 Blood Collection and Serum Separation

From each subject; 6-8 milliliter (ml) of PB was collected by vein puncture. The collected samples were divided into two portions; 2.5-3 ml of blood were placed in ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) tube for FC test and 3-5 ml of blood were placed in vacuum tube for serological tests as it was allowed to clot at room temperature, then centrifuged at 1500 round per minute for 10 min.

3.3.1.3 Storage and Transportation of Serum Samples

Each serum sample was divided into several aliquots and stored at -20 C° until needed for serological investigation.

The stored sera were transported in cooling box to Teaching Laboratories/Baghdad Medical City to perform the serological tests.

3.3.1.4 Storage and Transportation of Blood Samples

The EDTA blood was transported in cooling box (within 6-7 hrs after collection) to a Specialist Laboratory to perform the FC test.

3.3.2 Body Mass Index (BMI)

Body Mass Index uses mathematical formula based on person's height and weight; BMI equals weight (in Kilogram) divided by height in (square meters). It was suggested that a BMI of 19-24.9 indicates person of normal weight, a person with BMI of 25-29.9 is overweight, while a person with BMI of ≥ 30 is obese, and in the same regard a person with BMI < 19 is underweight [125].

3.3.3 Endoscopic Assessment of Gastritis

Endoscopic gastritis was diagnosed by the modified criteria of the Sydney system which involves subjective assessment of presence or absence of the possible findings as of the following: erythema, congestion, oedema, mosaic-like pattern, erosive gastritis, hemorrhagic gastritis, nodularity and polyps. The gastric and duodenal

mucosa was evaluated during endoscopy to find any ulcer [119 and 126].

3.3.4 Biopsies Examination

3.3.4.1 Histopathological Examination

Histological examination was conducted in Histology Laboratory of Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital/Baghdad Medical City and diagnosed by histopathologist. Each biopsy was used to make slide which then stained with H. and E. stains^{***} to examine histopathologic changes of gastric mucosa and demonstrate spiral microorganism.

3.3.4.1.1 Procedure

The procedure was followed according to [127 and 128].

3.3.4.1.2 Morphological Analysis "Sydney Classification"

Gastritis is best scored according to the updated Sydney System, in which a detailed histopathological classification was used to provide numerical data for statistical analysis. Categorization to mild, moderate and severe was divided into a score of 0-3 (none, mild, moderate and marked) [2 and 113].

The histopathological observations according to this classification are included; density of *H. pylori* colonization, degree of chronic inflammatory infiltrate, superficial epithelial damage, degree of inflammation activity and degree of IM [2 and 113].

However, the application of the standard method of Sydney Classification by the histopathologists in the Histology Laboratory of Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital/Baghdad Medical City was not followed precisely and many of the descriptive terms were unmatched with the above mentioned classifications.

***= Preparation method as it is indicated in appendix B.

Accordingly, in this study the assessment of the degree of inflammation that revealed by histopathology examination was a mixture of the standard Sydney Classification terms and the corresponding alternative terms used by histopathologists in the above mentioned laboratories.

3.3.5 CD4⁺CD25⁺ (Treg) Count

Regulatory T cells (CD4⁺CD25⁺) count was conducted at a specialist laboratory center in Baghdad.

3.3.5.1 Flow Cytometry Principle

A flow cytometer is versatile in its capability of measuring multiple parameters simultaneously. These parameters include the physical properties of cells (e.g., cell size and cytoplasmic granularity), surface membrane, cytoplasmic and nuclear Ags, and DNA-ribonucleic acid (RNA) contents of individual cells in a cell suspension. Surface, cytoplasmic and nuclear Ags are detected by means of fluorochrome conjugated Abs. These Ags are thus the extrinsic properties of the cell. The physical properties of the cell are the intrinsic properties, because no exogenous reagents are added for their detection. These parameters are measured through an optical system, and the light signal thus generated is registered in an electronic system. The computer system is responsible for data storage, gating and graphic display on a screen (see Figs. 3.2 and 3.3) [129].

Figure (3.2): Basic structure of a flow cytometer showing the fluid transportation system, the optical system, the electronic system and the cells sorter [129]

Figure (3.3): Schematic illustration showing the relationship of light scatter and cell size/structure [129]

Figure 3.4 shows an example of the dot plot cytogram (scattergram). This is a graphic display of dots as determined by two related parameters along the x and y axes. For instance, one can plot forward-angle light scatter against right-angle light scatter; each dot represents a single cell or event. On the basis of cell size (forward angle) and cytoplasmic granularity (right angle), the scattergram usually shows three distinct groups of cells in PB samples. The lymphocytes are the smallest (with no cytoplasmic granules); the monocytes are the largest; the granulocytes have the most cytoplasmic granules [129].

Figure (3.4): Scattergram with forward scatter plotted against side scatter, showing clusters of lymphocytes (red), monocytes (blue) and granulocytes (green) in a PB specimen [129]

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 showed a two-parameter histogram computes the percentage of cell groups as determined by two parameters (e.g., two monoclonal antibodies (MCA)). Dot plots can be used for this two-dimensional analysis [129]. These Figs showed the percentage of the Treg ($CD4^+CD25^+$), as its estimated by using mouse anti-human CD4 fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-conjugated MCA and mouse anti-human CD25 phycoerythrin (PE)-conjugated MCA. Figure 3.5 shows the low percentage of these cells, while Fig. 3.6 showed the high percentage of it.

Figure (3.5): Scattergram plotted by CD4 (FITC) versus CD25 (PE), in a PB specimen

Figure (3.6): Scattergram plotted by CD4 (FITC) versus CD25 (PE), in a PB specimen

3.3.5.2 Erythrocyte Lysing Reagent Kit

3.3.5.2.1 Contents of the Kit

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Reagent A for Leukocyte Fixation	1	25 ml
Reagent B for Erythrocyte Lysing	1	500 ml
Instruction Manual	1	-

3.3.5.2.2 Intended Use

This kit designed for an erythrocyte lysing with a complete preservation of the surface proteins and practically no loss of cells. It is particularly suitable for absolute cell counting and for assays, demanding a minimum loss of leukocytes. Residual debris does not need to be removed by centrifugation due to the properties of the lysing reagent buffer.

3.3.5.3 Mouse Anti-human CD4 (FITC), CD25 (PE), Dual Color

3.3.5.3.1 Contents of the Kit

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Mouse Anti-human CD4 (FITC), CD25 (PE)	1	-
Instruction Manual	1	-

3.3.5.3.2 Intended Use

Suitable for use in FC. Other applications not tested.

3.3.5.3.3 Form

Supplied as a liquid in 10 micromilliliter phosphate buffer saline, pH 7.2, 1% bovine serum albumin, 0.05% sodium azide. Dual color combination consisting of FITC conjugated and R-PE conjugated MCA mixed in optimal ratio.

3.3.5.3.4 Specificity

Recognizes human CD4 and CD25. React with normal human PB lymphocytes: CD4⁺CD25⁻: 23.8%, CD4⁻CD25⁺: 7.5%, CD4⁺CD25⁺: 11.5%.

3.3.5.4 Reagent's Preparation

All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.5.5 Samples Preparation

All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.5.6 Assay Procedure

The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions. The FC data were analyzed with FCS 4 EXPRESS software. Lymphocytes were gated via their forward and side scatter properties, at least 10000 cell/ μ l. Regulatory T cells were identified based on their expression of CD4 and CD25 via using anti-CD4 (FITC) and anti-CD25 (PE) conjugated MCA.

3.3.6 Serological Tests

Serological tests were conducted in Teaching Laboratories/Baghdad Medical City.

3.3.6.1 *OnSite H. pylori* Ab Combo Rapid Test

3.3.6.1.1 Test Principle

The *OnSite H. Pylori* Ab Combo Rapid Test is a lateral flow chromatographic immunoassay based on the principle of the double Ag–sandwich technique. The test cassette consists of (see Fig. 3.7):

1. A burgundy colored conjugate pad containing *H. Pylori* Ags including *CagA* conjugated with colloid gold (*H. Pylori* conjugates) and rabbit IgG-gold conjugates.
2. A nitrocellulose membrane strip containing a test band (T band) and a control band (C band). The T band is pre-coated with non-conjugated *H. Pylori* Ags, and the C band is pre-coated with goat anti-rabbit IgG.

When an adequate volume of test specimen is dispensed into the sample well of the cassette, the specimen migrates by capillary action across the cassette. The Abs either the IgG, the IgM or the IgA, to *H. pylori* if present in the specimen will bound to the *H. pylori* conjugates. The immunocomplex is then captured on the membrane by the pre-coated *H. pylori* Ags, forming a burgundy colored T band, indicating a *H. pylori* Abs positive test result.

Absence of the T band suggests a negative result. The test contains internal control (C band) which should exhibit a burgundy colored band of the immunocomplex of goat anti-rabbit IgG/rabbit IgG-gold conjugate regardless the presence of any Abs to *H. Pylori*. Otherwise, the test result is invalid and the specimen must be retested with another device.

Figure (3.7): Test principle of *OnSite H. Pylori Ab* combo rapid test

3.3.6.1.2 Contents of the Kit

1. Each kit contains 25 or 30 test devices, each sealed in a foil pouch with three items inside:
 - a. One cassette device.
 - b. One pipette dropper.
 - c. One desiccant.
2. Sample diluent (1 bottle, 5 ml).
3. One package inserts (instruction for use).

3.3.6.1.3 Sensitivity and Specificity

- Relative Sensitivity: 86.7%
- Relative Specificity: 91%
- Overall Agreement: 89.8%

3.3.6.1.4 Assay Procedure

The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.1.5 Interpretation of Assay Result

1. Negative Result: If only the C band was developed, the test indicated that no detectable Abs to *H. Pylori* were present in the specimen. The result was negative (see Fig. 3.8).

Figure (3.8): Negative result of *OnSite H. Pylori* Ab combo rapid test

2. Positive Result: If both C and T bands were developed, the test indicated for the presence of Abs to *H. Pylori* in the specimen. The result was positive (see Fig. 3.9).

Figure (3.9): Positive result of *OnSite H. Pylori* Ab combo rapid test

3. Invalid Result: If no C band was developed, the assay was invalid regardless of color development on the T band as indicated below (see Fig. 3.10). The assay was repeated with a new device.

Figure (3.10): Invalid result of *OnSite H. Pylori* Ab combo rapid test

3.3.6.2 Serum Anti-*H. Pylori* Ab (IgG) Level Assay

3.3.6.2.1 Principle of the Assay

The *H. pylori* IgG Ab test kit is based on the principle of the ELISA. *Helicobacter pylori* Ag is bound on the surface of the microtiter strips. Diluted patient serum or ready-to-use standards are pipetted into the wells of the microtiter plate. A binding between the IgG Abs of the serum and the immobilized *H. pylori* Ag takes place. Then ready-to-use anti-human-IgG peroxidase conjugate is added followed by the substrate (tetramethylbenzidine (TMB)) solution. The color development is terminated by the addition of a stop solution, which changes the color from blue to yellow. The resulting dye is measured spectrophotometrically at the wavelength of 450 nanometer (nm). The concentration of the IgG Abs is directly proportional to the intensity of the color.

3.3.6.2.2 Contents of the Kit

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
<i>H. pylori</i> Ag Coated Microtiter Strips	12	-
Calibrator A (Negative Control)	1	2 ml
Calibrator B (Cut-Off Standard)	1	2 ml
Calibrator C (Weak Positive Control)	1	2 ml
Calibrator D (Positive Control)	1	2 ml
Enzyme Conjugate	1	15 ml
Substrate	1	15 ml
Stop Solution	1	15 ml
Sample Diluent	1	60 ml
Washing Buffer	1	60 ml (10x concentrate)
Instruction Manual	1	-

3.3.6.2.3 Sensitivity and Specificity

- Clinical Sensitivity: 96%
- Clinical Specificity: 96%

3.3.6.2.4 Reagent's Preparation

All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.2.5 Samples Preparation

All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.2.6 Assay Procedure

The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.2.7 Calculation of Results

The obtained optical density (OD) of the standards was plotted on the y-axis (linear) against their concentration on the x-axis (logarithmic) either on semi-logarithmic graph paper or using an automated method.

The standard curve was calculated by applying each signal of the standards. The concentration of samples was read from the standard curve (see Fig. 3.11).

Figure (3.11): Standard curve of anti-*H. Pylori* Ab (IgG)

3.3.6.2.8 Interpretation of Results

U/ml	Interpretation
≤12	Negative
>12	Positive

3.3.6.3 Serum Anti-*CagA* Ab (IgG) Assay

3.3.6.3.1 Principle of the Assay

The microtiter plate provided in this kit has been pre-coated with specific *H. pylori CagA* Ag. Samples are then added to the appropriate microtiter plate wells and incubated. Then add horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated–anti-human IgG to each well and incubate. Finally, substrate solutions are added to each well. The enzyme-substrate reaction is terminated by the addition of a sulphuric acid solution and the color is measured spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 450 nm ± 2 nm.

3.3.6.3.2 Contents of the Kit

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Assay Plate	1	-
Positive Control	1	1 ml
Negative Control	1	1 ml
Enzyme Conjugate	1	10 ml
Substrate A	1	5 ml
Substrate B	1	5 ml
Stop Solution	1	5 ml
Sample Diluent	1	20 ml
Washing Buffer	1	20 ml (25x concentrate)
Adhesive Strip	4	-
Instruction Manual	1	-

3.3.6.3.3 Specificity

This immunoassay kit recognizes *CagA* Ab (IgG). No significance cross-reactivity or interference was observed.

3.3.6.3.4 Reagent's Preparation

All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.3.5 Samples Preparation

All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.3.6 Assay Procedure

The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.3.7 Calculation of Results

If the OD of the negative control < 0.1 , was calculated as 0.1.

While $OD_{\text{sample}}/OD_{\text{negative}} \geq 2.1$: Positive.

While $OD_{\text{sample}}/OD_{\text{negative}} < 2.1$: Negative.

3.3.6.4 Serum Parietal Cell Autoantibodies Level Assay

3.3.6.4.1 Principle of the Assay

Highly purified pig parietal cell H^+/K^+ -ATPase is bound to microwells. Antibodies to this Ag, if present in diluted serum, bind in the microwells. Washing of the microwells removes unbound serum Abs. Horseradish peroxidase conjugated anti-human IgG immunologically bind to the bound patient Abs forming a conjugate/Ab/Ag complex. Washing of the microwells removes unbound conjugate. An enzyme substrate in the presence of bound conjugate hydrolyzes to form a blue color. The addition of an acid stops the reaction forming a yellow end-product. The intensity of this yellow color is measured photometrically at 450 nm. The amount of color is directly proportional to the concentration of IgG Abs present in the original sample.

3.3.6.4.2 Contents of the Kit

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Highly Purified Pig H ⁺ /K ⁺ -ATPase, a- and b-subunits Coated Microtiter Strips	12	-
Calibrator A	1	1.5 ml (0 U/ml)
Calibrator B	1	1.5 ml (6.3 U/ml)
Calibrator C	1	1.5 ml (12.5 U/ml)
Calibrator D	1	1.5 ml (25 U/ml)
Calibrator E	1	1.5 ml (50 U/ml)
Calibrator F	1	1.5 ml (100 U/ml)
Positive Control	1	1.5 ml
Negative Control	1	1.5 ml
Enzyme Conjugate	1	15 ml
Substrate	1	15 ml
Stop Solution	1	15 ml
Sample Diluent	1	20 ml (5x concentrate)
Washing Buffer	1	20 ml (50x concentrate)
Instruction Manual	1	-

3.3.6.4.3 Sensitivity

The lower detection limit for anti-parietal cell has been determined at 0.5 U/ml.

3.3.6.4.4 Specificity

The microplate is coated with highly purified H⁺/K⁺-ATPase from pig parietal cells. The test kit is specific only for autoantibodies against the parietal cell Ag.

3.3.6.4.5 Reagent's Preparation

All reagents were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.4.6 Samples Preparation

All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.4.7 Assay Procedure

The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.4.8 Calculation of Results

The ODs of the calibrators were plotted against their concentration either on lin-log graph paper or using an automated method. The best fitting curve approximating the path of all calibrator points was drawn. The concentration of samples was estimated from calibration curve (see Fig. 3.12) by interpolation.

Figure (3.12): Parietal cell autoantibodies standard curve

3.3.6.4.9 Interpretation of Results

In a normal range study with serum samples from healthy blood donors the following ranges have been established with the anti-parietal cell test:

Anti-Parietal Cell-Ab	
Normal	<10 U/ml
Elevated	≥10 U/ml

3.3.6.5 Serum IL-17A Level Assay

3.3.6.5.1 Principle of the Assay

This assay employs the quantitative sandwich EIA technique. Antibody specific for IL-17A has been pre-coated onto a microplate.

Standards and samples are pipetted into the wells and any IL-17A present is bound by the immobilized Ab. After removing any unbound substances, a biotin-conjugated Ab specific for IL-17A is added to the wells. After washing, avidin conjugated HRP is added to the wells. Following a wash to remove any unbound avidin-enzyme reagent, a substrate solution is added to the wells and color develops in proportion to the amount of IL-17A bound in the initial step. The color development is stopped and the intensity of the color is measured.

3.3.6.5.2 Contents of the Kit

Components/Reagents	Quantity	Volume
Assay Plate	1	-
Standard (freeze dried)	2	-
Biotin-antibody	1	120 μ l (100x concentrate)
HRP-avidin	1	120 μ l (100x concentrate)
Biotin-antibody Diluent	1	10 ml
HRP-avidin Diluent	1	10 ml
Substrate	1	10 ml
Stop Solution	1	10 ml
Sample Diluent	1	20 ml
Washing Buffer	1	20 ml(25x concentrate)
Adhesive Strip	4	-
Instruction Manual	1	-

3.3.6.5.3 Sensitivity

The minimum detectable dose of human IL-17A is typically less than 1.56 picogram (pg)/ml. The sensitivity of this assay, or Lower Limit of Detection was defined as the lowest protein concentration that could be differentiated from zero.

3.3.6.5.4 Specificity

This assay has high sensitivity and excellent specificity for detection of human IL-17A. No significant cross-reactivity or interference between human IL-17A and analogues was observed.

3.3.6.5.5 Reagent's Preparation

All reagents were prepared and diluted according to the manual manufacturer's instructions. Washing solution was diluted into 1/25 with distilled water, biotin-Ab solution was diluted into 1/100 with biotin-Ab diluent, HRP-avidin solution was diluted 1/100 with HRP-avidin diluent, whereas a 2-fold dilution series of standard solution was prepared using the stock standard solution and a ready-to-use sample diluent as it is shown in Fig. 3.13.

3.3.6.5.6 Samples Preparation

All samples were prepared according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

3.3.6.5.7 Assay Procedure

The assay procedure was followed according to the manual manufacturer's instructions.

Figure (3.13): 2-fold dilution series of standard of IL-17A

3.3.6.5.8 Calculation of Results

The ODs of the standards were plotted on the x-axis against their concentration on the y-axis either on lin-log graph paper or using an

automated method. The best fitting curve approximating the path of all standard points was drawn. The concentration of samples was estimated from standard curve (see Fig. 3.14).

Figure (3.14): IL-17A standard curve

3.3.7 Tabulation of the Results

Results tabulation was performed using, Microsoft Office Word 2007 and Microsoft Office Excel 2007 programs.

3.3.8 Statistical Analysis

The data was put on computer file for storage and analysis. Descriptive statistics included; the use of frequencies, relative frequencies, means, standard deviations and the Chi-Square statistical test was used to test for associations between variables, Yates correction formula and fisher exact test were applied for the Chi-Square test whenever its applicable Pearson Correlation was used for test the associations between means with the results being considered as statistically significant when the P-value was <0.05 . Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used for data description and analysis.

3.3.9 Classification Criteria

Basis of the classification criteria of 60 patients underwent OGD into *H. pylori*-associated patients and non-*H. pylori* associated patients (positive control):

Any THREE of the followings is considered as *H. pylori*-associated disease:

1. Endoscopy findings.
2. Detection of *H. pylori* bacteria in gastric biopsy by H. and E. stained histopathology sections.
3. Detection of ACG or active chronic superficial gastritis (ACSG) in gastric biopsy by H. and E. stained histopathology sections.
4. Detection of IM in gastric biopsy by H. and E. stained histopathology sections.
5. Serology *H. pylori* positive by immune-chromatography (Combo test) or ELISA (IgG anti-*H. pylori*).

These criteria are based in part on Sydney classification and other histopathology/endoscopic features of *H. pylori*-associated diseases.

CHAPTER FOUR
RESULTS AND
DISCUSSION

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the basis of classification criteria as it is mentioned in the materials and methods, table 4.1 demonstrates the group classification of this study enrolled subjects.

Table (4.1): Classification of the study groups

Total Patients Underwent Endoscopy (n=60)						Healthy or Negative Control (NC)
<i>Helicobacter pylori</i> (Hp)- associated Patients (HPP)			Non Hp-associated Patients or Positive Control (PC)			
N ₀ =53			N ₀ =7			N ₀ =30
GS	GU	DU	GS	GU	DU	
N ₀ =28	N ₀ =8	N ₀ =17	N ₀ =4	N ₀ =0	N ₀ =3	

Certain tables are placed in the appendix F because we think that their results, in spite of being of great values, are not appertaining with the main aims of this study. These include; smoking and alcoholism status, family history, BMI, gender, age, disease duration, primary endoscopic and histopathology diagnosis, and primary endoscopic findings in duodenum and oesophagus.

Signs and symptoms in patients subjected to OGD are shown in table 4.2. The highest frequency (FR) among both HPP and PC was the epigastric pain/heartburn (96.2% and 85.7%, respectively), followed by nausea/vomiting (75.5% and 71.4%, respectively). The lowest frequent sign or symptom was diarrhea; 26.4% and 14.3% among HPP and PC, respectively. However, the differences in the frequencies of signs and symptoms between HPP and PC were not significant except for the weight loss ($p < 0.05$).

Table (4.2): Distribution of signs and symptoms in patients underwent OGD

Signs and Symptoms/Groups		HPP (n=53)	PC (n=7)	Total (n=60)	<i>p-value</i>
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
Dyspepsia	Present	28(52.8)	5(71.4)	33(55)	>0.05**
	Absent	25(47.2)	2(28.6)	27(45)	
Epigastric Pain/Heart Burn	Present	51(96.2)	6(85.7)	57(95)	>0.05**
	Absent	2(3.8)	1(14.3)	3(5)	
Weight Loss	Present	31(58.5)	1(14.3)	32(53.3)	<0.05*
	Absent	22(41.5)	6(85.7)	28(46.7)	
GIT Bleeding	Present	15(28.3)	1(14.3)	16(26.7)	>0.05**
	Absent	38(71.7)	6(85.7)	44(73.3)	
Nausea/Vomiting	Present	40(75.5)	5(71.4)	45(75)	>0.05**
	Absent	13(24.5)	2(28.6)	15(25)	
Diarrhea	Present	14(26.4)	1(14.3)	15(25)	>0.05**
	Absent	39(73.6)	6(85.7)	45(75)	

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Similar findings were noticed by other studies [130 and 131] which reported that epigastric pain/heart burn and nausea/vomiting are the main signs and symptoms in HPP and half of the *Hp*-infected patients revealed dyspepsia. A significant decrease in the body weight of *Hp*-infected patients compared to non-infected ones was noticed in this study which comes in consistency with some other studies which showed that the body weight increased significantly 12 months after eradication of *Hp*-infection [132]. The low frequency of GIT bleeding among *Hp*-infected patients had been found in other studies which reported that *Hp* infection would associated with a low risk for GIT bleeding [133]. Yet, no direct evidence links *Hp* infection and diarrhea [134], a concept comes in parallel with our results which showed lower incidence of diarrhea in *Hp*-infected patients, however, *Hp* infection has been linked to protein losing enteropathy [135] and to food allergies [136] which can cause diarrhea.

Table 4.3 shows the signs and symptoms frequency among different HPP subgroups (GS, GU and DU). Similar results were found as it was reviewed with table 4.2. Epigastric pain/heartburn was the

highest in frequency for all HPP subgroups (87.5%-100%), followed by nausea/vomiting (70.6%-78.6%) with no significant difference. Diarrhea was the lowest in frequency for all HPP subgroups (17.6%-50%) with no significant differences. Weight loss was the only sign/symptom that exhibited a significant elevated frequency ($p < 0.05$) among GU subgroup (87.5%) in comparison with GS subgroup (46.4%).

Table (4.3): Distribution of signs and symptoms in *Hp*-patient's subgroups

Signs and Symptoms/HPP		GS (n=28)	GU (n=8)	DU (n=17)	Total (n=53)
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)
Dyspepsia	Present	15(53.6)	3(37.5)	10(58.8)	28(52.8)
	Absent	13(46.4)	5(62.5)	7(41.2)	25(47.2)
Epi. Pain /Heart Burn	Present	27(96.4)	7(87.5)	17(100)	51(96.2)
	Absent	1(3.6)	1(12.5)	0(0)	2(3.8)
Weight Loss	Present	13(46.4)	7(87.5)	11(64.7)	31(58.5)
	Absent	15(53.6)	1(12.5)	6(35.3)	22(41.5)
GIT Bleeding	Present	11(39.3)	1(12.5)	3(17.6)	15(28.3)
	Absent	17(60.7)	7(87.5)	14(82.4)	38(71.7)
Nausea/ Vomiting	Present	22(78.6)	6(75)	12(70.6)	40(75.5)
	Absent	6(21.4)	2(25)	5(29.4)	13(24.5)
Diarrhea	Present	7(25)	4(50)	3(17.6)	14(26.4)
	Absent	21(75)	4(50)	14(82.4)	39(73.6)
<i>p-value</i>	>0.05** for all differences except for weight loss				

Epi.=Epigastric and **=Not Significant.

These results are in full agreement with other studies [2 and 137] which reported that the main presenting symptom of *Hp*-GS, -GU and -DU was epigastric pain. These studies showed also a high incidence of vomiting and moderate incidence of dyspepsia within *Hp*-GS patients. In other studies, GIT bleeding and diarrhea were found with low incidence among *Hp*-GS patients [138 and 139]. The results of the current study would work in with the above cited studies. In the above mentioned study [2], a low incidence of vomiting and GIT bleeding within *Hp*-PU patients, a low incidence of dyspepsia within *Hp*-GU patients, and a moderate incidence of dyspepsia within *Hp*-DU

patients were reported, results that are harmonized with ours, except that for nausea/vomiting, which was with high incidence in our study among *Hp*-PU patients. These incompatibilities in signs and symptoms presentations are highly affected by the intensity or severity of the disease which is mostly decided by both; the host factors, such as genetic make-up and environmental setting, and bacterial factors, such as the virulence of the infecting strain. One of the interesting findings of this study is the significantly higher incidence of weight loss within *Hp*-GU patients compared to *Hp*-GS and the not significantly higher incidence of weight loss within *Hp*-DU patients compared to *Hp*-GS patients. These findings are in accordance with one study [2] which reported only a quarter of the *HP*-GS patients with weight loss, and with another study [140] which concluded that there was no association between *Hp*-GS and BMI. Studies suggested that serum ghrelin concentrations are inversely related to the severity of *Hp*-associated diseases, and serum ghrelin levels increase after *Hp* cure for an increase in gastric ghrelin production, leading to body weight gain [141]. These findings may partially explain the BMI-associated above results.

Microscopic histopathological findings in patients subjected to OGD are shown in table 4.4. Three histopathological findings were significantly with higher frequency among HPP than PC group including the presence of ACG (69.8% Vs 28.6%), IM (39.6% Vs 0%), and visibility of *Hp* (83% Vs 14.3). On the other hand, two histopathological findings were significantly with lower frequency among HPP than PC group including the presence of hyperplasia/polyps (0% Vs 14.3%), and adenocarcinoma (0% Vs 14.3%), however, these results were negligible for the very few representative numbers of these findings. The frequency differences for other

histopathological findings between the HPP and PC groups were not-significant.

Table (4.4): Microscopic/histopathology findings in patients underwent OGD

Histopathological Findings/Groups		HPP (n=53)	PC (n=7)	Total (n=60)	<i>p-value</i>
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
Type of GS	ACG	37(69.8)	2(28.6)	39(65)	<0.05* (for ACG)
	ACSG	3(5.7)	0(0)	3(5)	
	CG	5(9.4)	1(14.3)	6(10)	
	CSG	8(15.1)	4(57.1)	12(20)	
Intestinal Metaplasia	Present	21(39.6)	0(0)	21(35)	<0.05*
	Absent	32(60.4)	7(100)	39(65)	
Mucosal Fragmentation	Present	14(26.4)	3(42.9)	17(28.3)	>0.05**
	Absent	39(73.6)	4(57.1)	43(71.7)	
Mucosal Congestion	Present	4(7.6)	2(28.6)	6(10)	>0.05**
	Absent	49(92.5)	5(71.4)	54(90)	
Lymphoid Follicle	Present	3(5.7)	0(0)	3(5)	>0.05**
	Absent	50(94.3)	7(100)	57(95)	
Hyperplasia/ Polyps	Present	0(0)	1(14.3)	1(1.7)	<0.05*
	Absent	53(100)	6(85.7)	59(98.3)	
Hyperplasia/Glandular Lesion	Present	1(1.9)	0(0)	1(1.7)	>0.05**
	Absent	52(98.1)	7(100)	59(98.3)	
Glandular Destruction	Present	1(1.9)	0(0)	1(1.7)	>0.05**
	Absent	52(98.1)	7(100)	59(98.3)	
Adenocarcinoma	Present	0(0)	1(14.3)	1(1.7)	<0.05*
	Absent	53(100)	6(85.7)	59(98.3)	
Visibility of <i>Hp</i>	Seen	44(83)	1(14.3)	45(75)	<0.05*
	Not Seen	9(17)	6(85.7)	15(25)	

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Figures 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3 show H. and E. stained sections photographs of different histopathological findings in HPP group.

Figure (4.1): Antral biopsy taken from a 26 years old male with active chronic gastritis, antral glands are surrounded by lymphocytes (black arrows), neutrophils (blue arrows), and plasma cells (red arrows), H. and E. stains (x100)

Figure (4.2): Antral biopsy taken from a 46 years old female with intestinal metaplasia, H. and E. stains (x10)

Figure (4.3): Antral biopsy taken from a 45 years old male showing the relation of *Hp* to gastric surface epithelium, H. and E. stains (x100)

Most patients attended the Gastroenterology and Hepatology center and enrolled in this study had active inflammation accompanied by chronic cell infiltration, i.e.; "active chronic" gastritis as it is demonstrated in table 4.4 and Fig. 4.1, which is also well referred by [142]. Other types of inflammations including ACSG, CG, and CSG as illustrated in table 4.4 were also reported among HPP and PC patients but with less frequency than that of ACG. The current study results exhibited a significant association between *Hp* infection and frequency of ACG. This is in agreement with the results of other study [143]. On the other hand and in consistent with our results, a previous study had shown a low frequency of superficial gastritis among *Hp*-infected patients [144]. Some evidences indicated that *Hp* infection may provide the proper environment for atrophic gastritis and IM to occur [144 and 145]. In compatibility with these findings, our results exhibited a significant difference in the frequency of IM between infected and non-infected patients; a result was also reported by other study [144]. Our investigation showed that *Hp* density was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in infected patients (83%) compared to non-infected one (14.3%). Similar finding was reported by other study [2]. Previous studies indicated that *Hp* contributes to the gastric mucosal injury, through its direct pathogenic mechanism [88], but many other etiological factors contributes to the gastric mucosal damage such as chemicals [146]. The last two mentioned studies come in consistency with current study as it indicated no significant differences in the gastric mucosal damage between infected and non-infected one. Other results in the same table consider as negligible for the very few representative numbers of each finding.

In table 4.5, the microscopic histopathological findings in HPP subgroups are illustrated. No significant differences were found between HPP subgroups in the following histopathological findings: types of GS, mucosal fragmentation, mucosal congestion, and lymphoid folliculation, whereas two of the histopathological findings were completely absent from all HPP subgroups including hyperplasia/polyps and adenocarcinoma, but glandular hyperplasia, and glandular destruction were found in a very few number, therefore their statistical analysis was invalid. For the IM, the frequency was higher with significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the GU subgroup (87.5%) when compared with GS subgroup (25%) or DU subgroup (41.2%). The bacterial visibility by the stained histopathological section was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) among the members of the GS subgroup (96.4%) and GU subgroup (87.5%) when compared to the DU subgroup (58.8%).

Table (4.5): Microscopic/histopathology findings in the *Hp* patients underwent OGD

Histopathological Findings/HPP		GS (n=28)	GU (n=8)	DU (n=17)	Total (n=53)
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)
Type of GS	ACG	18(64.2)	7(87.5)	12(70.6)	37(69.8)
	ACSG	1(3.6)	1(12.5)	1(5.9)	3(5.7)
	CG	4(14.3)	0(0)	1(5.9)	5(9.4)
	CSG	5(17.9)	0(0)	3(17.7)	8(15.1)
	<i>p-value</i>	>0.05** for all			
Intestinal Metaplasia	Present	7(25)	7(87.5)	7(41.2)	21(39.6)
	Absent	21(75)	1(12.5)	10(58.8)	32(60.4)
	<i>p-value</i>	GU X GS, DU <0.05*, GS X DU >0.05**			
Mucosal Fragmentation	Present	8(28.6)	1(12.5)	5(29.4)	14(26.4)
	Absent	20(71.4)	7(87.5)	12(70.6)	39(73.6)
	<i>p-value</i>	>0.05** for all			
Mucosal Congestion	Present	3(10.7)	0(0)	1(5.9)	4(7.6)
	Absent	25(89.3)	8(100)	16(94.1)	49(92.5)
	<i>p-value</i>	>0.05** for all			
Lymphoid Folliculation	Present	2(7.1)	0(0)	1(5.9)	3(5.7)
	Absent	26(92.9)	8(100)	16(94.1)	50(94.3)
	<i>p-value</i>	>0.05** for all			
Hyperplasia/ Polyps	Present	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Absent	28(100)	8(100)	17(100)	53(100)
Hyperplasia/ Glandular	Present	0(0)	0(0)	1(5.9)	1(1.9)
	Absent	28(100)	8(100)	16(94.1)	52(98.1)
Glandular Destruction	Present	0(0)	0(0)	1(5.9)	1(1.9)
	Absent	28(100)	8(100)	16(94.1)	52(98.1)
Adenocacinoma	Present	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Absent	28(100)	8(100)	17(100)	53(100)
Visibility of <i>Hp</i>	Seen	27(96.4)	7(87.5)	10(58.8)	44(83)
	Not Seen	1(3.6)	1(12.5)	7(41.2)	9(17)
	<i>p-value</i>	GS, GU X DU <0.05*, GS X GU >0.05**			

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

It has been found that all strains of *Hp* induce a marked immune response with local lymphocyte, plasma cell, and neutrophils infiltration [142]. In respect to our results, most HPP subgroups cases exhibited ACG. The presence of both acute and chronic inflammatory components within colonized mucosa suggests that soluble mediators capable of attracting cells derived from varying lineage may be the key regulators in the development of gastritis. Interleukin-8 is a potent neutrophils and lymphocyte-activating chemotactic cytokine

(chemokine), and gastrointestinal epithelial cells secrete biologically activated IL-8 in response to infection with pathogenic bacteria [147]. Results in table 4.5 and Fig. 4.2 display the frequency of IM which was higher in *Hp*-GU patients in comparison to other HPP subgroups (GS and DU) with significant difference. In spite of the higher frequency of IM in *Hp*-DU patients than *Hp*-GS patients, the difference was not-significant. Convergent results were reported by some other studies [2, 148 and 149]. About the bacterial density that had been demonstrated by stained histopathology sections and in consistent with our findings, previous studies pointed out that *Hp* density was higher in *Hp*-GS and *Hp*-GU patients than in *Hp*-DU patients [2]. On the contrary, other study [150] reported that *Hp* density is significantly greater in the antrum of DU subjects than those without DU. Other study found that *Hp* density was higher in *Hp*-GU patients than in chronic gastritis [151]. The number and location of biopsy seems to play a crucial role in the controversial findings seen in different studies since there are often topographical differences in colonization density [152]. Another factor that also might play a role in the preciseness of the results is the stained-sections examiner who might miss low *Hp* density [153].

Table 4.6 shows that the vast majority of HPP were positive for serum IgG anti-*Hp* (92.5%) compared to NC (53.3%) and PC (28.6%) with a significant differences ($p < 0.05$). No significant difference in this value was recorded between GS, GU, and DU HPP subgroups. Concerning the mean titers of this parameter, the highest was in the HPP group (50.76 ± 34.777 U/ml) compared to the PC (9.31 ± 5.805 U/ml) and NC (27.95 ± 26.266 U/ml) with a significant differences. No significant differences were noticed between the HPP subgroups (GS X GU X DU).

Table (4.6): The results of IgG anti-*Hp* in all study groups

Test	Study Groups	+ve FR(%)			-ve FR (%)	Mean Titer (U/ml)±SD	
		L-M	H-VH	Total			
IgG anti- <i>Hp</i>	NC N ₀ =30	8 (26.7)	8 (26.7)	16 (53.3)	14 (46.7)	27.95 ±26.266	
	PC N ₀ =7	2 (28.6)	0 (0)	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)	9.31 ±5.805	
	HPP N ₀ =53	GS N ₀ =28	14 (50)	12 (42.9)	26 (92.9)	2 (7.1)	43.12 ±31.022
		GU N ₀ =8	2 (25)	6 (75)	8 (100)	0 (0)	63.56 ±26.946
		DU N ₀ =17	6 (35.3)	9 (52.9)	15 (88.2)	2 (11.8)	57.31 ±41.943
		Total N ₀ =53	22 (41.5)	27 (51)	49 (92.5)	4 (7.5)	50.76 ±34.777
	Total	90(100%)	32 (35.6)	35 (38.9)	67 (74.5)	23 (25.5)	39.9 ±18.922
<i>p-value</i>	For FR%: NC X PC <0.05*, HPP X NC, PC <0.05*, other differences are not significant (NS). For the mean titers: HPP X PC, NC <0.05*, NC X PC <0.05*, within the HPP subgroups all differences are NS.						

L-M=Low to Medium, H-VH=High to Very High and *=Significant.

In the above table, the mean titer and frequency of serum IgG anti-*Hp* were higher in HPP group compared to NC and PC groups with a significant difference. In general, the serum levels of IgG anti-*Hp* Abs were increased in the presence of infection and could be used as a marker [124]. In the same above table, results revealed no significant difference in the serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs levels between non-ulcer, and PU cases of *Hp*-infected patients. This result is in accordance with another study [154], which reported that *Hp* serology cannot be used to predict the presence or absence of gastro-duodenal ulcer disease. In the current study, the seroprevalence of serum IgG anti-*Hp* among NC which represents (for a large extent) asymptomatic *Hp* infected was 53.3%, whereas in other studies it was ranging from 38.9%-67.9% (according to the age) in Indian [155], 46.6% in South Koreans [156], 64.2% in Iranian children [157], 51% in Saudis [158], 70% in

American blacks and 34% in American whites [159], and 44.4% in Germans [160]. Generally speaking, the rate of *Hp* infection tends to be higher in developing countries as South America and Asia (>80%) than developed countries as Europe (25-60%) [161]. Indeed, factors such as family history of gastric disease, source of drinking water, number of siblings, sharing beds, and level of hygiene have been linked to acquisition of *Hp* infection [162]. Urgent questions related to this issue would need answers; from the 53.3% of the seropositive healthy people, who is really has an active *Hp* infection in the current time? Who are of these people would actually develop an *Hp*-associated disease in the future? Is there any way for preventing such development? And is there any possible test that can predict these future developments? To answer these questions, further deep future investigations are needed.

In the present study, the PB CD4⁺CD25⁺ T regulatory cell count had exhibited an increased and significant moderate-high level frequency in most subjects of the HPP (73.6%) and PC (71.4%) groups compared to a low frequency in this parameter (46.7%) among the subjects of NC group (Table 4.7). The differences in frequency % within the subgroups of the HPP group were not significant. The difference in the mean count between the HPP and/or PC (25.67±16.971 % and 19.72±9.70 %, respectively) and NC (13.56±8.026 %) groups was significant ($p < 0.05$), whereas all other differences in the mean count between other study groups were not significant.

Table (4.7): The results of Treg cell count in all study groups

Test	Study Groups	M-H FR(%)	L-N FR(%)	Mean Count (%)±SD	
Treg	NC N ₀ =30	14(46.7)	16(53.3)	13.56±8.026	
	PC N ₀ =7	5(71.4)	2(28.6)	19.72±9.70	
	HPP N ₀ =53	GS N ₀ =28	20(71.4)	8(28.6)	25.7±17.04
		GU N ₀ =8	6(75)	2(25)	28.0±19.65
		DU N ₀ =17	13(76.5)	4(23.5)	24.5±16.54
	Total N ₀ =53	39(73.6)	14(26.4)	25.67±16.971	
Total	90(100%)	58(64.4)	32(35.6)	21.2±12.232	
<i>p-value</i>	For FR%: PC X NC <0.05*, HPP X PC >0.05**, HPP X NC <0.05*, (other differences within the HPP subgroups are NS). For the mean count: PC X NC <0.05*, HPP X NC <0.05*, HPP X PC >0.05**, (other differences within the HPP subgroups are NS).				

M-H=Moderate to High, L-N=Low to Normal, *=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Helicobacter pylori induce a host immune response, but the persistence of the infection suggests that the response is not effective in eliminating the infection. Furthermore, multiple lines of evidences suggest that the immune response contributes to the pathogenesis associated with the infection [97]. Several studies have noted that the Th cell response to *Hp* is polarized, since CD4⁺ T cells in the gastric mucosa of infected individuals produce the Th1 cytokines IL-12 and IFN- γ , whereas IL-4, a Th2 cytokine production by these T cells, is absent [163]. Another subset of CD4⁺ T cells is T regulatory cells (CD4⁺CD25⁺ Treg), which produce IL-10 and TGF- β [164]. The presence of Treg in the PB of *Hp* infected individuals could inhibit the response of CD4⁺ T cells to *Hp* [165]. Hence, this may help explain the inability of the host response to eliminate the infection due to the activation of Treg cells, which were recently reported to be increased in the gastric mucosa of *Hp*-infected individuals and were described as CD4⁺, CD25^{high} and forkhead box P₃⁺ (FOXP₃) [97].

The results of the current study (Table 4.7) had exhibited a significant elevation in the PB Treg cell count, and in the mean titer of

HPP group when compared to NC, however, this elevation was not significant when compared to PC group. This result would come in consistency with the above mentioned role of Treg cell in inhibiting the inflammatory mechanism of the Th1 as the main effector cell in *Hp* infection which benefit the host in subsiding the inflammatory response on one hand and benefit the bacterial colonization and long persistent on the other hand. In the same table, there was no difference in PB Treg cell count and in the mean titer among the subgroups of HPP (GS, GU and DU). Some studies showed that patients with PU had reduced Treg response compared to those without ulcers [166], but other studies showed that Treg cells had an increased level in all types of *Hp*-associated diseases with a positive association with endoscopic findings of gastro-duodenal diseases and histological grade but negatively associated with IM in gastritis and PU groups [167].

For serum IL-17A in this study, most of the HPP and PC subjects (79.2% and 71.4%, respectively) were with an elevated level (Table 4.8) compared to the NC (53.3%) with a significant difference ($P < 0.05$). However, no significant differences were noticed between HPP subgroups for this parameter. The mean titer for serum IL-17A was highest in the HPP group (14 ± 7.23 pg/ml) compared to PC (13.4 ± 4.74 pg/ml) and NC (10.66 ± 2.96 pg/ml) with a significant difference between HPP and NC groups (Table 4.8). However, no significant differences were observed in between HPP subgroups.

Table (4.8): The results of IL-17A in all study groups

Test	Study Groups	H FR(%)	L-N FR(%)	Mean Titer (pg/ml)±SD	
IL-17A	NC N ₀ =30	16(53.3)	14(46.7)	10.66±2.96	
	PC N ₀ =7	5(71.4)	2(28.6)	13.4±4.74	
	HPP N ₀ =53	GS N ₀ =28	23(82.1)	5(17.9)	15.2± 9.31
		GU N ₀ =8	7(87.5)	1(12.5)	12±1.82
		DU N ₀ =17	12(70.6)	5(29.4)	12.9±4.00
	Total N ₀ =53	42(79.2)	11(20.8)	14±7.23	
Total	90(100%)	63(70)	27(30)	12.9±6.60	
<i>p-value</i>	For FR%: PC X NC <0.05*, HPP X NC <0.05*, HPP X PC >0.05** (other comparisons are NS). For the mean titers: PC X NC <0.05*, HPP X NC <0.05*, HPP X PC >0.05** (other comparisons are NS).				

H=High, L-N=Low to Normal, *=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Interleukin-17A plays a dual role in the *Hp* infection as it exerts anti-inflammatory effects on *Hp*-induced gastritis through suppression of Th1 differentiation in animal model on one hand [95] and induces the secretion of IL-8 which attracts neutrophils promoting inflammation on the other hand [168]. This contradictory dual effect is best seen in infection and vaccination. In infection, Treg suppress the inflammatory reaction driven by IL-17 thereby favoring bacterial persistence. In immunization, *Hp*-specific memory Th cells are produced that can possibly alter the ratio between Th17 and Treg responses so that the IL-17-driven inflammatory reaction can overcome the Treg response leading to bacterial clearance [168]. In agreement with the above cited studies, serum IL-17A level is higher in *Hp*-infected patients than in NC. These findings suggest that IL-17A may play an important role in the pathogenesis of *Hp*-related gastric inflammation and the subsequently developing gastric ulceration. Similar results were recently reported [169]. The same table (Table 4.8) shows no significance difference in serum IL-17A level between HPP subgroups, a result which agreed with another study [170].

The ratio between the mean count of PB Treg cells and the mean titer of serum IL-17A in different study groups is shown in table 4.9. This ratio was higher in HPP group (1.8:1) in comparison with PC group (1.4:1) and NC group (1.2:1). The same mean ratio profile was demonstrated for the subjects with elevated Treg cell count as the highest ratio was noticed within the HPP group (2.1:1) compared to other control groups (1.9:1 and 1.7:1 in PC and NC groups, respectively).

Table (4.9): Mean counts of PB Treg cells and mean titers of serum IL-17A and their ratio in all study groups

HPP (n=53)								
Total (n=53)			Normal-Low Treg			Elevated Treg (n=39)		
Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*
Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A	
25.6	14	1.8:1	9.9	11.7	0.8:1	31.5	14.8	2.1:1
PC (n=7)								
Total (n=7)			Normal-Low Treg (n=2)			Elevated Treg (n=5)		
Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*
Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A	
19.7	13.4	1.4:1	7.9	15	0.5:1	24.4	12.7	1.9:1
NC (n=30)								
Total (n=30)			Normal-Low Treg			Elevated Treg (n=14)		
Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*
Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A	
13.5	10.6	1.2:1	6.9	9.7	0.7:1	21.2	11.8	1.7:1

Mean ratio*=Treg Mean Count:IL-17A Mean Titer.

Comparing the ratio between the mean count of PB Treg cells and the mean titer of serum IL-17A within the HPP subgroups (Table 4.10) reveals that this ratio was in its highest level in the GU subgroup (3:1) compared to the other two subgroups of HPP; GS (2:1), and DU (2:1).

Table (4.10): Mean counts of PB Treg cells and mean titers of serum IL-17A and their ratio in HPP subgroups

GS (n=28)								
Total (n=28)			Normal-Low Treg (n=8)			Elevated Treg (n=20)		
Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*
Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A	
25.7	15.2	1.7:1	8.7	12.8	0.7:1	32.5	16.2	2:1
GU (n=8)								
Total (n=8)			Normal-Low Treg (n=2)			Elevated Treg (n=6)		
Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*
Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A	
28	12	2.3:1	10.3	13.5	0.8:1	33.8	11.4	3:1
DU (n=17)								
Total (n=17)			Normal-Low Treg (n=4)			Elevated Treg (n=13)		
Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*	Mean		Mean ratio*
Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A		Treg	IL-17A	
24.5	12.9	1.9:1	10	8.1	1.2:1	29	14.3	2:1

Mean ratio*=Treg Mean Count:IL-17A Mean Titer.

Results shown in tables 4.9 and 4.10 illustrate the relationship between PB Treg and serum IL-17A activities. According to these results the response of the Treg was higher than IL-17A in all study groups, and highest in HPP compared to controls. The same results were reported within HPP subgroups (GS, GU and DU), and these results may predict that the *Hp* infected patients underwent an ineffective immune response due to the hyper-activation of Treg, a result come into full consistency with other previous study [96]. In the same tables, the results showed that when the Treg activity was high, the IL-17A activity was low and vice versa, except in DU patients in which the IL-17A level was lower than Treg in both low and high counts Treg cases. These results confirm that Th17 and Treg cells are developmentally related and exist in a delicate balance that can dictate the outcome of a bacterial infection. The development of Th17 in human being depends on a cytokine milieu rich in IL-1 β , IL-6 and TGF- β that initiates the differentiation process and IL-23 that participates in the expansion and maintenance of the Th17 cells. The

current consensus is that the Th17 and Treg cell commitments are mutually controlled and TGF- β is required for the differentiation of both Th17 and Treg cells by inducing their key transcription factors, retinoid-related orphan receptor γ (ROR γ t) or (RORc) and FOXP₃, respectively [96]. However, in the absence of IL-6, an exclusive Treg differentiation occurs as FOXP₃ is able to associate with and to inhibit ROR γ t. Otherwise, in the presence of IL-6, this inhibition is abrogated allowing Th17 differentiation [171]. Paradoxically, the gastric concentration of IL-6 was elevated but serum concentration was not elevated in *Hp*-infected individuals [172]. One might hypothesize that these results are due to the higher concentration of TGF- β in the gastric milieu of *Hp*-infected individuals. At low concentrations, TGF- β synergizes with IL-6 to promote IL-23 receptor (IL-23r) expression favoring Th17 cell commitment. High concentrations of TGF- β ; however, repress IL-23r expression and favor FOXP₃ Treg cell differentiation [173].

The results of PCA in all study groups are demonstrated in table 4.11. The total frequency of positive serum PCA was 22/90 (24.5%) in all study groups. This frequency was higher in HPP group 16/53 (30.2%) compared to NC 6/30 (20%), and PC groups 0/7 (0%). These differences were significant ($P < 0.05$) when compared between HPP and PC groups, but not-significant ($P > 0.05$) when compared between HPP and NC groups. Among the HPP subgroups, the frequency % of positive serum PCA was high in both GS (42.9%) and GU (37.5%) subgroups compared to the DU subgroup (5.9%) with significant differences ($P < 0.05$). The mean titer of positive serum PCA cases in different study groups exhibited a similar profile to that of the frequency % results. The HPP group exhibited the highest mean titer (37.5 ± 11.99 U/ml) in comparison with the NC group (12.7 ± 3.67

U/ml) and PC group (0 U/ml) with significant differences ($P < 0.05$). No significant differences were detected in the PCA mean titer between the GS and GU subgroups of HPP. For DU subgroup, the *p-value* was not done because of the low number of patients (only one patient was positive for PCA).

Table (4.11): The results of PCA in all study groups

Test	Study Groups	+ve PCA Frequency and Mean		-ve FR(%)	
		FR(%)	Mean Titer (U/ml)±SD		
PCA	NC N ₀ =30	6(20)	12.7±3.67	24(80)	
	PC N ₀ =7	0(0)	-	7(100)	
	HPP N ₀ =53	GS N ₀ =28	12(42.9)	40.1±12.23	16(57.1)
		GU N ₀ =8	3(37.5)	27.3±9.89	5(62.5)
		DU N ₀ =17	1(5.9)	37.6± 13.47	16(94.1)
		Total N ₀ =53	16(30.2)	37.5±11.99	37(69.8)
Total	90(100%)	22(24.5)	22.9±8.88	68(75.5)	
<i>p-value</i>	For FR%: HPP X PC <0.05*, HPP X NC >0.05**, GS, GU X DU <0.05*, GS X GU >0.05**. For mean titers: HPP X PC, NC <0.05*, GS X GU >0.05**.				

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Previous studies reported that PCA is the serological hallmark of symptomatic autoimmune gastritis (AIG) in humans [174, 175 and 176]. Several clinical and epidemiological studies indicate that most patients with AIG have or have had *HP* infection [84]. Consistent with these findings our results showed a significant relationship between *Hp* infection and the incidence of PCA. Previous studies suggested the presence of PCA was associated with a greater than twofold reduced prevalence for DU [102]. In agreement with these studies our results reported low prevalence of PCA among DU subgroup. Furthermore, autoantibodies against epitopes on canalicular structures within parietal cells, where the major autoantigen in classic autoimmune gastritis is located [177], could also inhibit parietal cell function in patients with *Hp* gastritis [102]. This could lead to the unchanged or

even decreased basal acid secretion despite raised gastrin concentrations in *Hp* infected subjects without DU [102], a possible explanation for the reduced rate of DU in the group with PCA found in our study. However, these hypotheses need to be investigated further. Some evidence suggested that apparently healthy individuals may harbor H⁺K⁺-ATPase-autoreactive CD4⁺ T cells that have escaped from negative selection in the thymus, as reflected by the occasional presence of H⁺K⁺-ATPase-specific autoantibodies [7]. Consistent with this evidence, PCA was detected in 20% of NC group in our study.

In table 4.12, the correlation between the frequency and mean titer of positive PCA with IgG anti-*Hp* in HPP and NC groups is shown. All positive PCA in HPP group (16/53) were with positive IgG anti-*Hp* result with a mean titer of 37.5 U/ml. In the NC group, all PCA positive subjects (6/30) were also with positive IgG anti-*Hp* result with a mean titer of 12.2 U/ml. The difference in the mean titer between the two groups was significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table (4.12): Correlation between the frequency and mean titer of positive PCA with IgG anti-*Hp* in HPP and NC groups

Positive PCA	IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i>		Mean Titer (U/ml)±SD
	Result	FR(%)	
HPP N ₂ =16/53 (30.2%)	Positive	16/16(100)	37.5±11.99
	Negative	0/16(0)	-
	Total	16/16(100)	37.5±11.99
NC N ₂ =6/30 (20%)	Positive	6/6(100)	12.7±3.67
	Negative	0/6(0)	-
	Total	6/6(100)	12.7±3.67
Total N ₂ =22/90 (24.5%)	Positive	22/22(100)	22.9±8.88
	Negative	0(0)	-
<i>p-value</i>	HPP mean X NC mean <0.05*		

*=Significant.

In this study, the prevalence of serum IgG anti-*Hp* was very high (100%) among PCA positive cases, but in another study, 62% of the patients with pernicious anemia and severe atrophic corpus gastritis had positive *Hp* serology [178]. In one further study, out of 28

individuals with severe autoimmune type gastric atrophy six were *Hp* positive in histology (21.4%) and another 13(46.4%) were positive in serology (altogether 68% positive for *Hp*) [179]. In a Swedish study, however, 83% of patients with pernicious anemia had Abs against *Hp* [180].

In table 4.13, the correlation between PCA positivity and the serum IL-17A and PB Treg activities is illustrated. There was no significant difference between positive or negative PCA in the frequency of high level or low-normal level as well as mean titer of the serum IL-17A. The same was true for the PB Treg cell count.

Table (4.13): Correlation of PCA positivity with IL-17A and Treg activity

Parameters			IL-17A		
			High FR(%)	Normal or low FR(%)	Mean Titer (pg/ml)±SD
PCA	HPP	+ve N ₀ =16	13(81.3)	3(18.7)	14.68±11.10
		-ve N ₀ =37	29(78.4)	8(21.6)	13.66±4.87
	NC	+ve N ₀ =6	2(33.3)	4(66.7)	9.40±1.48
		-ve N ₀ =24	14(58.3)	10(41.7)	10.97±3.16
Parameters			Treg		
			High FR(%)	Normal or low FR(%)	Mean count (%)±SD
PCA	HPP	+ve N ₀ =16	13(81.3)	3(18.7)	30.54±17.87
		-ve N ₀ =37	26(70.3)	11(29.7)	23.57±16.36
	NC	+ve N ₀ =6	2(33.3)	4(66.7)	11.76±8.70
		-ve N ₀ =24	12(50)	12(50)	14.01±7.98
<i>p-value</i>			>0.05** for all differences		

**=Not Significant.

There are some evidences suggested that Th17 involve in immunopathology of AIG [181 and 182], but the same authors [181 and 182] were concluded that IL-17-producing Th17 cells mediated AIG disease could be inhibited by suppression Th17 activity due to Treg activity. Consistent with the above findings, our results showed (Table 4.13) no significant difference in serum IL-17A level between PCA positive and negative cases. A possible explanation for this, due

to Treg response was higher than IL-17A response in our study. Another study indicated that the depletion of Treg did not result in gastric autoimmune disease unless the frequency of autoreactive T cells was elevated [13]. In agreement with the last mentioned study, the results of the current study exhibited no significant difference in PB Treg activity between PCA positive and negative one. However, *Hp*-driven chronic Th1-mediated inflammation may be sufficient to abrogate CD4⁺CD25⁺ Treg suppression, leading to activation of H⁺K⁺-ATPase-specific CD4⁺ T cells and subsequent gastric autoimmunity. A second scenario also involves thymic escape by H⁺K⁺-ATPase-specific autoreactive T cells, but in addition, genetics predisposes a host to develop gastric autoimmunity if this host expresses particular HLA alleles that can facilitate the presentation of both H⁺K⁺-ATPase epitopes and *Hp* peptides [84 and 183], all these factors should be of an effect on the PCA production.

All study groups were tested for serum anti-*Hp* Abs (all isotypes) by the immunochromatography Combo test. The results of this qualitative test are shown in table 4.14. The highest frequency % was noticed as expected in the HPP group (77.4%) compared to 42.9% and 20% in the PC and NC groups, respectively. The differences in these frequencies were significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table (4.14): The results of combo test in all study groups

Test	Study Groups	+ve FR(%)	-ve FR(%)	
Combo	NC N ₀ =30	6(20)	24(80)	
	PC N ₀ =7	3(42.9)	4(57.1)	
	HPP N ₀ =53	GS N ₀ =28	22(78.6)	6(21.4)
		GU N ₀ =8	6(75)	2(25)
		DU N ₀ =17	13(76.5)	4(23.5)
	Total N ₀ =53	41(77.4)	12(22.6)	
Total	90(100%)	50(55.6)	40(44.4)	
<i>p-value</i>	HPP X PC, NC <0.05*, PC X NC >0.05**, all other differences are >0.05**.			

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Nearly everyone infected with *Hp* develops specific Abs, which is found in serum and in gastric aspirates or extracts of stomach. Accordingly, elevated titers of IgG and IgA Abs directed against *Hp* Ags are previously documented in *Hp*-infected people [97]. Immunoglobulin M and IgA-producing cells in biopsies from the antral region of the *Hp*-infected patient's stomachs were 40- to 50-fold higher in frequency than, in non-infected subjects [97]. Consistent with these findings our results showed a significant difference in Combo test results (as test for all isotypes Abs detection) between infected and non infected individuals.

The frequency of the *Hp* strains (*CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻) in IgG anti-*Hp* positive subjects is listed in table 4.15. The total frequency of *CagA*⁺ strains was 25/67 (37.3%) in all study groups. The frequency was 40.8% in HPP group, 50% in PC group, and 25% in NC group. The difference in frequency between *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ was significant in HPP and NC groups ($p < 0.05$). The level of serum IL-17A was high for both *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains, but with no significant difference between the two strains, in the majority of subjects for HPP and PC groups, and low for NC group. The difference in the frequency between high and low-normal level of serum IL-17A within each

group for *CagA*⁺ or *CagA*⁻ strains separately was significant in HPP and PC groups and not-significant in the NC group. Similar results were noticed for the Treg cell count in all study groups.

Table 4.16 illustrates the serum IL-17A level and PB Treg cell count according to *CagA* strain classification of IgG anti-*Hp* positive subjects in HPP subgroups. All results in this table were in a similar profile to that in table 4.15. The difference in the positivity rate between all subgroups was not significant as they were ranging from 88.2% in DU group to 100% in GU group. The frequency of *CagA*⁺ strains were always lower than *CagA*⁻ strains in total sum of the subgroups with a total percents of 40.8% and 59.2% for *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻, respectively. Within each subgroup, the difference between *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ frequency was significant in GS and GU subgroups and non-significant in DU subgroup. The level of serum IL-17A was generally high in all subgroups irrespective of being *CagA*⁺ or *CagA*⁻ and the difference in the frequency between subjects with high and low-normal level of serum IL-17A was significant for all subgroups of HPP as well as for the total sum of the subgroups. The same results profile was documented with the PB Treg cell count as it is clear in the table.

Table (4.15): IL-17A level and Treg cell count according to *CagA* strain classification of IgG anti-*Hp* positive subjects in all study groups

Positive IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i>	<i>CagA</i> Strains FR(%)	IL-17A Level FR(%)		Treg Cell Count FR(%)	
		High	Low-Normal	High	Low-Normal
HPP N ₀ =49/53 (92.5)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 20/49(40.8)	15/20(75)	5/20(25)	13/20(65)	7/20(35)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 29/49(59.2)	25/29(86.2)	4/29(13.8)	24/29(82.8)	5/29(17.2)
	Total 49/49(100)	40/49(81.6)	9/49(18.4)	37/49(75.5)	12/49(24.5)
PC N ₀ =2/7 (28.6)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 1/2(50)	1/1(100)	0/1(0)	1/1(100)	0/1(0)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 1/2(50)	1/1(100)	0/1(0)	1/1(100)	0/1(0)
	Total 2/2(100)	2/2(100)	0/2(0)	2/2(100)	0/2(0)
NC N ₀ =16/30 (53.3)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 4/16(25)	0/4(0)	4/4(100)	0/4(0)	4/4(100)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 12/16(75)	8/12(66.7)	4/12(33.3)	6/12(50)	6/12(50)
	Total 16/16(100)	8/16(50)	8/16(50)	6/16(37.5)	10/16(62.5)
Total N ₀ =67/90 (74.4)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 25/67(37.3)	16/25(64)	9/25(36)	14/25(56)	11/25(44)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 42/67(62.7)	34/42(81)	8/42(19)	31/42(73.8)	11/42(26.2)
	Total 67/67(100)	50/67(74.6)	17/67(25.4)	45/67(67.2)	22/67(22.8)
<i>p</i> -value					
HPPXPC<0.05* HPPXNC<0.05* PCXNC<0.05*	+ve X -ve <0.05* for HPP, NC and Total	H X L <0.05* for HPP,PC and total		H X L <0.05* for all groups and total	

*=Significant.

Table (4.16): IL-17A level and Treg cell count according to *CagA* strain classification of IgG anti-*Hp* positive subjects in HPP subgroups

Positive IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i>	<i>CagA</i> Strains FR(%)	IL-17A Level FR(%)		Treg Cell Count FR(%)	
		High	Low-Normal	High	Low-Normal
GS N ₂ =26/28 (92.9)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 9/26(34.6)	8/9(88.9)	1/9(11.1)	6/9(66.7)	3/9(33.3)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 17/26(65.4)	14/17(82.4)	3/17(17.6)	13/17(76.5)	4/17(23.5)
	Total 26/26(100)	22/26(84.6)	4/26(15.4)	19/26(73.1)	7/26(26.9)
GU N ₂ =8/8 (100)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 3/8(37.5)	2/3(66.6)	1/3(33.3)	2/3(66.6)	1/3(33.3)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 5/8(62.5)	5/5(100)	0/5(0)	4/5(80)	1/5(20)
	Total 8/8(100)	7/8(87.5)	1/8(12.5)	6/8(75)	2/8(25)
DU N ₂ =15/17 (88.2)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 8/15(53.3)	5/8(62.5)	3/8(37.5)	5/8(62.5)	3/8(37.5)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 7/15(46.7)	6/7(85.7)	1/7(14.3)	7/7(100)	0/7(0)
	Total 15/15(100)	11/15(73.3)	4/15(26.7)	12/15(80)	3/15(20)
Total N ₂ =49/53 (92.5)	<i>CagA</i> ⁺ 20/49(40.8)	15/20(75)	5/20(25)	13/20(65)	7/20(35)
	<i>CagA</i> ⁻ 29/49(59.2)	25/29(86.2)	4/29(13.8)	24/29(82.8)	5/29(17.2)
	Total 49/49(100)	40/49(81.6)	9/49(18.4)	37/49(75.5)	12/49(24.5)
<i>p-value</i>					
>0.05**	+ve X -ve <0.05* for GS, GU and Total	H X L <0.05* for all groups and total in <i>CagA</i> ⁺ and <i>CagA</i> ⁻		H X L <0.05* for all groups and total in <i>CagA</i> ⁺ and <i>CagA</i> ⁻	

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

The cytotoxin-associated gene A was the first gene found to be differentially present in *Hp* isolates and is considered a marker for the presence of the Cag-PAI [184]. Cytotoxin-associated gene A and other virulent factors in *Hp* clinical isolates as *VacA* have been proposed as related to more severe gastric diseases in adults [184], although some reports indicate that a high prevalence of *CagA* gene is found irrespective of the disease developed [185]. Other studies reveal that the presence of *CagA* is not a reliable marker for prediction of digestive disorders caused by *Hp* infection [186].

In the current study, the prevalence of *CagA*⁺ strains was less than *CagA*⁻ strains in HPP, NC groups as well as in the total subjects enrolled in this study with a significant difference (Table 4.15). This result was unusual when it compared with many other studies in

different places in the world as 78% to 80% in Turkey [187], 82% in Japan [188], 93% in Nigeria [189], 97% in China [190], 61.6% in Tunisia [191], and 47.6% to 63.4% in Mexico [192]. The majority of those studies pointed out that in patients with DU, the *CagA* positivity rate is relatively higher than in patients with gastritis or GU which is in agreement with our study that found that the prevalence of *CagA*⁺ strains is higher in DU patients than gastritis and GU. This finding referred also that *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains have an equal chance of developing *Hp*-associated diseases and the final clinical outcome is weakly associated with the type of *Hp* strain. In some Western countries, *CagA*-positive status has been associated with severe clinical outcomes [193], whereas in Asian countries, the associations of *CagA* status and severity of the diseases were not observed [194]. To explain such variation in the disease outcome of *CagA*⁺ strains in different geographical and ethnic groups in the world, there might be other factors; environmental and genetic of both the host and bacteria. One of these bacterial genetic factors is the *VacA* virulence genotype or alleles. It has been found that s1a, s1b and m1a *VacA* alleles have a higher prevalence in European, African and American strains, whereas the *VacA* s1c and m1b alleles are more prevalent in Asian strains [195]. Further studies are required to clarify the types of *VacA* alleles and their role in the pathogenesis of *Hp* in Iraq.

In the same tables the results revealed no significance different in serum IL-17A and PB Treg activities between *CagA*⁺ or *CagA*⁻ cases and these results agreed with other previous studies which showed no association between the *CagA* status and the gastric IL-17A level or TGF- β [96], and the absence of different in TGF- β level between *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ cases may help in explanation why there are no significant different in Treg level between both *Hp* strains.

Table 4.17 illustrates the correlation of PCA positively and *CagA* strain in all study groups. Surprisingly, the PCA positivity was higher in frequency % in *CagA*⁻ rather than *CagA*⁺ with significant differences ($P<0.05$) in HPP group and the total sum of the groups.

Table 4.18 demonstrates the correlation of the serum IgG anti-*Hp* positive mean titer with the *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains. The mean titer of serum IgG anti-*Hp* positive subjects was higher among the *CagA*⁺ than *CagA*⁻ subjects in GS, GU, and NC groups as well as the total sum of the groups with significant differences ($p<0.05$), whereas it was lower in *CagA*⁺ than *CagA*⁻ subjects in DU group with no significant difference ($p>0.05$).

Table (4.17): PCA positive subjects in correlation with *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains

№ of PCA Positive Subjects in Each Study Groups/ <i>CagA</i> Strains		FR(%) of Positive PCA		<i>p</i> -value
		<i>CagA</i> ⁺	<i>CagA</i> ⁻	
HPP №=53	GS №=12/28	3(25)	9(75)	-
	GU №=3/8	0(0)	3(100)	-
	DU №=1/17	1(100)	0(0)	-
	Total №=16/53	4(25)	12(75)	<0.05*
PC №=0/7		-	-	-
NC №=6/30		2(33.3)	4(66.7)	-
Total For All Groups №=22/90		6(27.3)	16(72.7)	<0.05*

*=Significant.

Table (4.18): Mean titer of IgG anti-*Hp* positive subjects in correlation with *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains

№ of IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i> Positive Subjects in Each Study Groups/ <i>CagA</i> Strains		Mean Titer of Positive IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i> (U/ml)		<i>p</i> -value
		<i>CagA</i> ⁺	<i>CagA</i> ⁻	
HPP №=53	GS №=26/28	61.3	37.8	<0.05*
	GU №=8/8	88.9	48.3	<0.05*
	DU №=15/17	56.2	67.2	>0.05**
	Total №=49/53	63.4	46.7	<0.05*
PC №=2/7		18.2	14.8	-
NC №=16/30		56.6	41.9	<0.05*
Total For All Groups №=67/90		60.5	44.6	<0.05*

*=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Before the era of *Hp*, first degree relatives of patients with pernicious anemia were shown to have more corpus but not antrum atrophy than controls [196]. Atrophic changes of the corpus can be determined by blood tests, such as low serum pepsinogen I, high serum gastrin, and PCA positivity [197], the serum PCA positively consider as indicator of atrophic change in the corpus [198]. It has been shown that atrophic corpus gastritis develops more often in *CagA*⁺ than in *CagA*⁻ patients [199]. In addition, a clear correlation between atrophic antral gastritis and *CagA* seropositivity has been demonstrated [200]. In the present study, the *CagA*⁺ strain was not associated with PCA positivity; however the positive frequency % was significantly higher in *CagA*⁻ strain than *CagA*⁺ strain. Many possible explanations of these results; first, patients with positive PCA showed higher scores in gastric atrophy of corpus than patients with negative PCA [201], second, *CagA* positivity was not associated with atrophic gastritis in the corpus but was associated with atrophic antral gastritis [197]. There are some evidences to suggest that *Hp CagA*⁺ strains could modulate the immune response to *Hp* [202], which is in consistence with these findings shown in table 4.18 in which the serum IgG anti-*Hp* mean titer is higher in *CagA*⁺ strains than *CagA*⁻ strains with significance difference. These results agreed with other previous study [203]. In the same table, the only exception for this rule was in the DU group in which the mean titer of serum IgG anti-*Hp* was lower in *CagA*⁺ than *CagA*⁻ infected subjects with no significant value. This result was in agreement with other study which stated that such result could be associated with allelic combinations of the *Hp* that has certain preference to duodenum rather than stomach [195].

The correlation of histopathology gastritis with the serological/immunological tests and *Hp*-bacterial intensity are illustrated in table

4.19. The positive results of Combo test and the histopathology gastritis was almost with positive correlation for all types of gastritis except CG. The same was true for the correlation between serum IgG anti-*Hp*, serum IgG anti-*CagA*, serum PCA, PB Treg, *Hp* visibility in stained sections, and serum IL-17A and every type of gastritis. However, there were no significant differences between these correlations within each of the histopathology gastritis and each of the serology/immunology markers or *Hp* visibility in stained sections.

Table (4.19): Correlation of histopathology gastritis with serological/immunological findings and *Hp* bacterial intensity in HPP group

Tests/ Histopathology Gastritis		ACG (n=37) FR(%)	ACSG (n=3) FR(%)	CG (n=5) FR (%)	CSG (n=8) FR(%)	Total (n=53) FR(%)	
Combo	+ve	30(81.1)	2(66.7)	2(40)	7(87.5)	41(77.4)	
	-ve	7(18.9)	1(33.3)	3(60)	1(12.5)	12(22.6)	
IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i>	-ve	3(8.1)	0(0)	1(20)	0(0)	4(7.5)	
	+ve	L-M	14(37.8)	1(33.3)	2(40)	5(62.5)	22(41.5)
		H-VH	20(54.1)	2(66.7)	2(40)	3(37.5)	27(51)
	Total	34(91.9)	3(100)	4(80)	8(100)	49(92.5)	
IgG Anti- <i>CagA</i>	+ve	14(37.8)	3(100)	1(20)	4(50)	22(41.5)	
	-ve	23(62.2)	0(0)	4(80)	4(50)	31(58.5)	
PCA	+ve	12(32.4)	2(66.7)	2(40)	0(0)	16(30.2)	
	-ve	25(67.6)	1(33.3)	3(60)	8(100)	37(69.8)	
Treg	L-N	10(27)	2(66.7)	0(0)	2(25)	14(26.4)	
	M-H	21(56.8)	1(33.3)	3(60)	3(37.5)	28(52.8)	
	VH	6(16.2)	0(0)	2(40)	3(37.5)	11(20.8)	
<i>Hp</i> Visibility	Not Seen	9(24.3)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	9(17)	
	Seen	28(75.7)	3(100)	5(100)	8(100)	44(83)	
<i>p-value</i>		All differences are >0.05**					
IL-17A	Mean Titer±SD	13.8±7.7	10.4±3.0	10.8± 1.9	18.3±6.5	14±7.23	
<i>p-value</i>		All differences are >0.05**					

L-M=Low to Medium, H-VH=High to Very High, L-N=Low to Normal, M-H=Moderate to High, VH=Very High and **=Not Significant.

More than 90% of *Hp*-infected patients have detectable serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs, and the vast majority of *Hp*-infected patients have ACG in the antral biopsy specimens [154]. Hence, the status of *Hp* infection is a crucial confounding factor in analyzing the relationship between

Abs levels and histological gastritis. If non-*Hp*-infected patients are included in the analysis, the correlation between Abs levels and gastritis scores or *Hp* density may be misleading due to their common association with the status of *Hp* [154]. In this study we found no significant differences in serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs levels between all histological gastritis types. In contrast to our findings, one study reported that serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs levels correlated with the grades of antral PMN leukocyte infiltration [204], however, in a harmony with our findings, another study demonstrated that having higher levels of IgG anti-*Hp* Abs implies advanced antral gastritis with either acute or chronic inflammation [205]. The correlation between anti-*Hp* Abs levels and the severity of histological gastritis or *Hp* density has been studied with conflicting results [206]. This discrepancy in results may arise from differences in classification and grading of gastritis, the numbers of subjects, consideration of confounding factors, and statistical methods [154]. In the same last table, results reported no significant differences between *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains in their correlation with histological gastritis types, however, these results were consistent with other previous findings which showed that *CagA* status was not associated with a significant higher scores for chronic inflammation, activity, *Hp* density, or IM [207].

Previous studies showed there were two different forms of AIG that can be differentiated; the active form, which is characterized, in particular, by pre-glandular lymphocytic infiltration, with local destruction of corpus glands and hypertrophy of parietal cells, and the "burned out" form, which involves complete atrophy of parietal cells, with only low grade chronic infiltrates persisting [113]. However, the two forms were associated serologically with Abs against parietal cells and/or intrinsic factors [113 and 208]. Consistent with these findings

our results showed no significant difference in PCA positivity between each type of histological gastritis. The presence of neutrophil activity in the positive PCA gastric sections was due to *Hp* infection, because the most common histological gastritis in *Hp*-infected patients is ACG [142 and 154]. There are some evidences that reported a positive correlation between Treg activity and the histological grade of the specimens, including acute inflammation, chronic inflammation, and lymphoid follicle number [167]. In agreement with these evidences, our results showed positive correlations between Treg activity and each type of histological gastritis with no significant difference between each of them. This type of correlations between the acute grade and chronic grade of inflammatory gastric mucosa and the grade of *Hp* density has been reported by other studies [209], however, this positive correlation was reported in our findings, was with no significant difference in *Hp* colonization between each type of histological gastritis. In the same table, our results showed no significant difference in serum IL-17A activity between each type of histological gastritis, and it was positively correlated with each of them. In consistent with this finding, another study had found that IL-17 and IL-8 levels were significantly correlated with the number of infiltrating mononuclear cells and neutrophils [10], and this indicate that IL-17 play important role in the acute and chronic gastritis.

Table 4.20 expresses the correlation of IM with the serological/immunological tests and *Hp*-bacterial intensity in HPP group. Among 21/53 with IM in the HPP group, 14/21 (66.7%) were with positive Combo test, 19/21 (90.5%) were with positive IgG anti-*HP* test, 9/21 (42.9%) were with positive IgG anti-*CagA* test, 5/21 (23.8%) were with positive PCA test, 17/21 (81%) with moderate-very high Treg cell count, and 17/21 (81%) with visible *Hp* in stained histology

sections. On the other hand 32/53 of the HPP group was without IM from which 27/32 (84.4%) were with positive Combo test, 30/32 (93.7%) were with positive IgG anti-*Hp* test, 13/32 (40.6%) were with positive IgG anti-*CagA* test, 11/32 (34.4%) were with positive PCA test, 22/32 (68.8%) were with moderate–very high Treg cell count, and 27/32 (84.4%) with visible *Hp* in stained histology sections. These results reveal no significant differences in the correlation between the presence and the absence of IM with any of the serological/immunological markers and *Hp* visibility in stained sections. The same result was reported for IL-17A mean titer.

Table (4.20): Correlation of intestinal metaplasia with the serological/immunological tests and *Hp* bacterial intensity in HPP group is illustrated

Tests/I. Metaplasia		Intestinal Metaplasia			
		Present (n=21)	Absent (n=32)	Total (n=53)	
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
Combo	+ve	14(66.7)	27(84.4)	41(77.4)	
	-ve	7(33.3)	5(15.6)	12(22.6)	
IgG Anti- <i>HP</i>	-ve	2(9.5)	2(6.3)	4(7.5)	
	+ve	L-M	5(23.8)	17(53.1)	22(41.5)
		H-VH	14(66.7)	13(40.6)	27(51)
		Total	19(90.5)	30(93.7)	49(92.5)
IgG Anti- <i>CagA</i>	+ve	9(42.9)	13(40.6)	22(41.5)	
	-ve	12(57.1)	19(59.4)	31(58.5)	
PCA	+ve	5(23.8)	11(34.4)	16(30.2)	
	-ve	16(76.2)	21(65.6)	37(69.8)	
Treg	L-N	4(19)	10(31.2)	14(26.4)	
	M-H	13(61.9)	15(46.9)	28(52.8)	
	VH	4(19.1)	7(21.9)	11(20.8)	
<i>HP</i> Visibility	Not Seen	4(19)	5(15.6)	9(17)	
	Seen	17(81)	27(84.4)	44(83)	
<i>p-value</i>		All differences are >0.05**			
IL-17A	Mean Titer±SD	12.2±2.21	15.2±8.99	14±7.23	
<i>p-value</i>		>0.05**			

I=Intestinal, L-M=Low to Medium, H-VH=High to Very High, L-N=Low to Normal, M-H=Moderate to High, VH=Very High and **=Not Significant.

The above table shows that the serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs levels did not alter in the presence or absence of IM, and it was positively correlated with both. Other studies had reported similar findings [210 and 211],

whereas another study had demonstrated that the serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs titer was related inversely to the extent of IM [212]. However, the above mentioned study [212] was conducted on asymptomatic non-confirm *Hp*-associated subjects, i.e. this study confirms the presence of IM by histopathological test and correlate it with serological IgG anti-*Hp* Abs regardless of the presence or absence of actual active *Hp* infection.

As previously illustrated in other studies [207], *CagA* status was not associated with significantly higher scores for chronic inflammation, activity, *Hp* density, or IM which come in consistent with this study.

In this study, no significant difference was detected in the incidence of IM between PCA positive and negative cases. As we illustrated previously, the presence of serum PCA was consider as indicator of atrophic change in the corpus [196, 197 and 198]. A reflection for closing results, were reported by [197] which stated that half of patients with atrophic corpus gastritis had IM, whereas, another study stated that the presence of IM considered a hallmark of severity of atrophic gastritis [213]. As it was presented in a previous study, Treg cells had expressed an increased level in all types of *Hp*-associated diseases with a positive association with endoscopic findings of gastro-duodenal diseases and histological grade but negatively associated with IM in gastritis and PU groups [167]. In contrast to that, this study results exhibited no alteration in the Treg cells activity in the presence or absence of IM, and was positively correlated with both. Previous studies found an increased level of TGF- β as well as Tregs in patients with *HP*-induced gastritis [214], which supports the notion that TGF- β is a critical differentiation factor for Treg cells within a local microenvironment [215 and 216]. It is interesting that recently reported a higher level of TGF- β expression in the presence of IM

[217]. Such a higher level of TGF- β expression might contribute to the higher numbers of Tregs in GS/PU patients with IM. However, further investigations would be required to explore this possibility.

This study results expressed no significant difference of the *Hp* colonization in the gastric mucosa between positive and negative IM cases, and the degree of bacterial colonization was positively correlated with both. Similar findings were reported by other studies [2 and 218]. Recent studies have suggested that IL-17 plays an important role in the inflammatory response to *Hp* infection and ultimately influences the outcome of the *Hp*-associated diseases [9, 95 and 219]. Consistent with these studies our results reported no significant difference in IL-17A activity between positive and negative IM cases, and its activity was positively correlated with both.

The correlation of *Hp* bacterial colonization as indicated by the *Hp* visibility and intensity in histopathology stained section with serological/immunological markers results are shown in table 4.21. Among 44/53 with visible *Hp* bacteria in stained histology sections, 36/44 (81.8%) were positive with Combo test, 41/44 (93.2%) were positive with IgG anti-*Hp* test, 17/44 (38.6%) were positive with IgG anti-*CagA* test, 16/44 (36.4%) were positive with PCA test, and 33/44 (75%) were with moderate-high level Treg cell count. On the other hand, among 9/44 with invisible (not seen) *Hp* bacteria in stained histology sections, 5/9 (55.6%) were with positive Combo test, 8/9 (88.9%) were with positive IgG anti-*Hp* test, 5/9 (55.6%) were with positive IgG anti-*CagA* test, 0/9 (0%) were with positive PCA test, and 6/9 (66.7%) were with moderate-high Treg cell count. In comparison between the frequencies of 'seen' and 'not seen' *Hp* bacteria and their correlation with any of the serological or immunological tests (except the PCA test) there were no significant differences ($p > 0.05$). For IL-

17A mean titer, the difference between those with seen bacteria (14.2 pg/ml) and not seen bacteria (12 pg/ml) was not significant ($p>0.05$).

Table (4.21): Correlation of *Hp* bacterial intensity in histopathology stained section with serological/immunological markers results in HPP group

Tests/ <i>Hp</i> Colonization		Not Seen (n=9)	Seen (n=44)				Total (n=53)	
			Low (n=31)	Mod (n=5)	High (n=8)	Total (n=44)		
			FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)		
Combo	+ve	5(55.6)	26(83.9)	3(60)	7(87.5)	36(81.8)	41(77.4)	
	-ve	4(44.4)	5(16.1)	2(40)	1(12.5)	8(18.2)	12(22.6)	
IgG Anti- <i>Hp</i>	+ve	L-M	2(22.2)	12(38.7)	2(40)	6(75)	20(45.5)	22(41.5)
		H-VH	6(66.7)	17(54.8)	2(40)	2(25)	21(47.7)	27(51)
		Total	8(88.9)	29(93.5)	4(80)	8(100)	41(93.2)	49(92.5)
	-ve	1(11.1)	2(6.5)	1(20)	0(0)	3(6.8)	4(7.5)	
IgG anti- <i>CagA</i>	+ve	5(55.6)	12(38.7)	2(40)	3(37.5)	17(38.6)	22(41.5)	
	-ve	4(44.4)	19(61.3)	3(60)	5(62.5)	27(61.4)	31(58.5)	
PCA	+ve	0(0)	13(41.9)	1(20)	2(25)	16(36.4)	16(30.2)	
	-ve	9(100)	18(58.1)	4(80)	6(75)	28(63.6)	37(69.8)	
Treg	L-N	3(33.3)	8(25.8)	1(20)	2(25)	11(25)	14(26.4)	
	M-H	6(66.7)	23(74.20)	4(80)	6(75)	33(75)	39(73.6)	
<i>p-value</i>		All differences are >0.05** except for PCA test is <0.05*						
IL-17A	Mean Titer±SD	12±3.11	15.3±8.99	12.1±2.57	12.1±2.7	14.2±5.9	14±7.23	
<i>p-value</i>		>0.05 **						

Mod=Moderate, L-M=Low to Medium, H-VH=High to Very High, L-N=Low to Normal, M-H=Moderate to High, **=Not Significant and *=Significant.

In table 4.21, serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs was elevated in case of the presence of helical bacteria in the gastric mucosa or its absence. In consistent with this finding, another study reported that IgG anti-*Hp* Abs levels in the antral mucosa was not correlated with the grade of *Hp* density (if only *Hp*-infected patients were analyzed) [154], whereas another study [211] noted that there was no significant increase in the serum IgG anti-*Hp* Abs levels in consistent with increasing the density of *Hp* in the mucosal biopsies.

As it was previously illustrated, *CagA* status was not associated with significantly higher scores for chronic inflammation, activity, *Hp* density, or IM [207]. Coinciding with these findings our results was also with no significant in the helical bacteria visibility (colonization)

between *CagA*⁺ and *CagA*⁻ strains. In this study, the PCA positivity was significantly correlated with helical bacterial visibility in the gastric stained sections. Matching our findings, another study was reported the same correlation [102]. BALB/c and transgenic mice studies were showed that the depletion of CD4⁺CD25⁺ Treg cells by administration of an anti-CD25 Abs either at the time of infection with *Hp* or during chronic infection and gastritis, did not affect bacterial colonization [13]. In agreement with these studies our results showed Treg activity did not affect bacterial load. Finally, this study reported that the serum IL-17A levels would not alter with increase or decrease bacterial colonization. One previous study showed that treatment of *Hp*-infected mice with an anti-IL-17 Abs but not a control Abs would significantly reduced the *Hp* burden and inflammation in the stomach [220]. However, the level of this cytokines in *Hp*-infected individuals depended upon many factors; presence of *VacA* m1 gene carriage strains, which recently reported significantly associated with increase the IL-17 and IL-23 mRNA expression in mucosa comparison to *VacA* m2 carriage strains [169], and levels of others cytokines such as; IL-1 β , IL-6, TGF- β , and IL-23 [96] as illustrated in pages (81-82).

CHAPTER FIVE
CONCLUSIONS AND
RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

1. The prevalence rate of *H. pylori* infection in apparently healthy and/or asymptotically infected individuals whom included in this study is 53.3%, which is much lower than those in Asian and non-Asian studied populations. On the other hand, the rate was 88.3% in symptomatically infected individuals whom attended mentioned hospital, which is similar to those in most of Asian and non-Asian studied populations.
2. Epigastric pain and heart burn are the most common sign/symptom among *H. pylori*-associated and non-*H. pylori* associated gastro-enteropathy with no significant difference between the two types. On the other hand, weight loss, although it was not the highest frequent sign/symptom among *H. pylori*-associated patients but it was the only one with significant difference between the *H. pylori*-associated and non-*H. pylori* associated gastro-enteropathy. The same mentioned conclusion was reported within HPP subgroups.
3. Detection of IgG anti-*H. pylori* in the serum of GIT patients is helpful in the avoidance of more invasive diagnostic tests as endoscopy and biopsy, but the levels of IgG anti-*H. pylori* Abs in the serum do not predict the presence of gastro-duodenal PU diseases or the density of *H. pylori* colonization.
4. Most HPP subjects were exhibited a high level of serum IL-17A and PB Treg cell counts. The Treg:IL-17A ratio is higher in HPP group than PC and NC groups, which concludes an ineffective immune response in the HPP due to the Treg count dominance over the IL-17A titer.
5. Prevalence of PCA was 20% in apparently healthy and/or asymptomatic infected Iraq people and 30.2% in *H. pylori*-associated patients which point out a considerable positive

relationship between *H. pylori* infection and gastric autoimmunity. The presence of PCA may be coincides with a protective level of DU development.

6. Treg count and IL-17A level expressed no significant effect on PCA positively, bacterial load, IM and type of histological gastritis.
7. Prevalence of IgG anti-*CagA* among positive IgG anti-*H. pylori* Iraqi people was 37.3% which is much lower than most other studied populations in the world.
8. The presence of *CagA*⁺ strain of *H. pylori* is not enough for the prediction of the type of *H. pylori*-associated disease as well as the severity of the disease; however, *CagA*⁺ strains play a role in the modulation of the immune response through elucidation of high titer of IgG anti-*H. pylori*.
9. *Helicobacter pylori* strain type has little and not significant effect on the IL-17A level and Treg cell counts in patients with *H. pylori* associated diseases.
10. Cytotoxin associated gene A has no role in induction of *H. pylori*-related AIG and not correlated with certain histopathological findings such as type of histological gastritis, presence or absent of IM and the bacterial density in the gastric stained sections. The mentioned histopathological findings were not correlated with serum IgG anti-*H. pylori* level or serum PCA positivity, except the bacterial colonization has certain role in induction of *H. pylori*-related AIG.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Antral and corpus mucosal pinch biopsies are recommended for each patient underwent OGD, because of the low sensitivity of endoscopy in detection of gastritis.
2. Further investigations are needed to clarify the correlation between *H. pylori*-associated diseases and certain human leukocyte Ags alleles as well as to determine which alleles associated with presentation of parietal cells autoantigens.
3. Further molecular/immunological study is needed to demonstrate the expression of FOXP₃ mRNA and ROR γ t mRNA in the gastric mucosa of *H. pylori* infected subjects and their correlation with CD4⁺CD25⁺ Treg count and Th17 (IL-17A) activity as well as to study the role of certain cytokines such as TGF β , IL-6, IL-23 and IL-1 β in induction and maintenance of both cells.
4. Further study is needed to correlate PCA positivity with the degree of corpus atrophy as well as with certain biochemical and haematological findings such as vitamin B12 level and severity of the pernicious anemia in *H. pylori*-infected individuals.
5. Immuno-genotyping is needed for *H. pylori* *VacA* and *IceA* virulent factors positive strains from Iraqi patients to find out any association with disease severity and their possible modulating effect on Treg and Th17 activities.
6. Studies are needed in the field of anti-CD25 MCA passive immunization for the improvement of immune response to *H. pylori* infection and clearance of bacteria from gastric mucosa.
7. Further study is required to elucidate the mechanisms by which *H. pylori* interacts with Th17 cells and how these cells facilitate infection. A better understanding of the nature, regulation, and function of Th cell responses to *H. pylori* may help to explore novel

and effective immunotherapies for gastric diseases induced by this organism.

8. To carry out deeper studies on the factors that play a role in the development of *H. pylori*-associated diseases among *H. pylori*-infected people and to investigate the possibility of designing a test that can predict such future developments.

CHAPTER SIX
REFERENCES

6. REFERENCES

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Appendices

Questionnaire Data Sheet

Patient No....., record No....., patient name....., residence....., occupation....., education level....., sex....., age....., date....., weight....., disease duration....., height....., and current medication.....

1-Are you:

- Smoking? Yes..... No.....
- Alcoholism? Yes..... No.....

2-Exclusion criteria

- Using NSAIDs (for the last 7 days).....
- Using corticosteroidal (for the last 4 weeks).....
- Presence of any autoimmune or chronic disease.....
- Recent surgery (during the last 6 months).....
- Taking any biological agents.....
- Recent blood transfusions (during the last 6 months).....
- Taking antimicrobial drugs (for the last 2 weeks).....

3-What is (are) usually the recurrence feeling?

- Dyspepsia.....
- Epigastric pain.....
- Heart burn.....
- Vomiting.....
- Weight loss.....
- GIT bleeding.....
- Upper abdominal discomfort.....
- Diarrhea.....
- Nausea.....
- Others.....

4-Are there any previous family history of diagnosed PU and/or gastritis? Yes..... No.....

5-Investigation:

a-Endoscopic findings:

-Oesophagus:

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-Stomach:

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-Duodenum:

D1:

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D2:

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-Conclusion:

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b-Histopathological findings:

-Gastric biopsy:

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-Duodenum biopsy:

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C-Serological Tests:

- *OnSite H. pylori* Abs Combo Rapid Test: ve⁺.....,ve⁻.....
- *H. pylori* IgG Abs Test: ve⁺.....,ve⁻.....,Titer.....
- Anti-parietal AbsTest: ve⁺.....,ve⁻.....,Titer.....
- Anti-*CagA* Abs Test: ve⁺.....,ve⁻.....
- IL-17A Test:

d-CD4⁺ and CD25⁺ (Treg) Flow Cytometry Test:

Preparation Method of H. and E. Stains

1. Harri's Haematoxylin

Haematoxylin Crystals.....	5 gm
Alcohol, absolute (ethanol).....	50 ml
Potassium Alum.....	100 gm
Distilled Water.....	1000 ml
Mercuric Oxide (red).....	2.5 gm

Haematoxylin had dissolved in alcohol; the alum in the water by the aid of heat. Then removed from heat and the two solutions mixed and boiled for less than 1 min with stirring (bringing to boiling should be rapid as soon as possible). Then removed from heat, and the mercuric oxide added slowly. Re-heated to a simmer until it becomes dark purple, removed from heat, and the vessel plunged into a basin of cold water till cooled. 2-4 ml of glacial acetic acid per 100 ml added (to increase the precision of nuclear stain). Filtered before use.

2. Eosin...as counter stain for Haematoxylin

1% stock alcoholic Eosin:

Eosin Y, water soluble.....	1 gm
Distilled Water.....	20 ml
Dissolved, and add.....	
Alcohol, 95%.....	80 ml

Working Eosin solution:

Eosin stock solution.....	1 part
Alcohol, 80%.....	3 parts

0.5 ml/100 ml of glacial acetic acid was added just before use with stirring.

(No filtration needs).

Kits and Device Images

Mouse Anti-human CD4 (FITC), CD25 (PE), Dual Color [USBiological, USA]

Onsite H. pylori Ab Combo Rapid Test [CTK Biotech, Inc, USA]

Helicobacter pylori IgG ELISA Kit [Demeditec, Germany]

Cytotoxin Associated Gene A (*CagA*) Ab (IgG) ELISA Kit [Cusabio, China]

Human Interleukin-17A (IL-17A/IL-17) ELISA Kit [Cusabio, China]

Parietal Cell Ab ELISA Kit [Demeditec, Germany]

Flow Cytometry (C4BE6) [Partec, Germany]

Appendix E

Variables/Cases	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
Strip	Positive	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x	x		x
	Negative																						x	x	x			x
Anti- <i>Hp</i> IgG	1-12		x																									
	13-30			x		x		x	x		x			x		x	x	x	x			x		x				
	31-60				x		x			x		x								x								x
	61-100	x										x		x							x					x	x	
	>100																						x					
Anti- <i>CagA</i> (IgG)	Positive	x				x					x			x						x	x	x	x			x		
	Negative		x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x	x						x	x		x	x
PCA	1-9	x	x		x	x		x	x		x			x			x	x	x			x	x		x	x	x	x
	10-25			x							x	x		x	x	x												
	26-45																											x
	46-60																											
	61-100																				x			x				
IL-17A	7-15				x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x	x
	16-30	x	x	x		x							x									x						
	31-60														x		x											
Treg	6-12		x		x	x	x																			x		x
	13-25	x												x											x		x	
	26-45			x							x	x	x		x	x						x		x				
	46-70									x	x							x	x	x	x		x					

Appendix E

29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	Total/Percentage			
x	x		x	x	x	x			x	x				x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x			x		x	x		x	44(73.33%)			
		x					x	x			x	x	x		x							x		x	x		x			x		16(26.67%)			
						x	x				x											x		x			x					9(15%)			
x	x				x					x							x						x								x	18(30%)			
		x	x					x	x			x																	x	x	x		14(23.33%)		
				x										x		x							x		x	x						14(23.33%)			
															x		x										x						5(8.34%)		
	x		x		x					x		x			x	x	x	x					x	x						x			24(40%)		
x		x		x		x	x	x	x		x		x	x			x						x			x	x	x	x		x	x	36(60%)		
	x	x	x		x	x	x	x		x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	44(73.33%)		
x									x																								8(13.33%)		
												x																	x				5(8.34%)		
																																		0(0%)	
				x																														3(5%)	
x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x				48(80%)		
	x																														x		x	10(16.67%)	
																																			2(3.33%)
		x										x					x	x					x	x										16(26.67%)	
x	x		x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x			x	x	x						x				x	x					x	22(36.67%)		
							x							x														x			x			13(21.66%)	
																													x	x					9(15%)

Table I. Association of different variables with study groups

Variables/ Groups		HPP (n=53)	PC (n=7)	NC (n=30)	Total (n=90)	<i>p-value</i>
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
BMI	UW	1(1.9)	0(0)	0(0)	1(1.1)	>0.05**
	NW	29(54.7)	5(71.4)	20(66.7)	54(60)	
	OW	14(26.4)	1(14.3)	8(26.7)	23(25.6)	
	O	9(17)	1(14.3)	2(6.7)	12(13.3)	
SM	Present	22(41.5)	4(57.1)	0(0)	26(28.9)	<0.05*
	Absent	31(58.5)	3(42.9)	30(100)	64(71.1)	
AL	Present	3(5.7)	1(14.3)	0(0)	4(4.4)	-
	Absent	50(94.3)	6(85.7)	30(100)	86(95.6)	
FH	Present	20(37.7)	2(28.6)	0(0)	22(24.4)	<0.05*
	Absent	33(62.3)	5(71.4)	30(100)	68(75.6)	
AG	18-29	19(35.9)	1(14.3)	16(53.3)	36(40)	>0.05**
	30-39	13(24.5)	2(28.6)	6(20)	21(23.3)	
	40-49	9(17)	3(42.9)	4(13.3)	16(17.8)	
	50-59	8(15.1)	1(14.3)	2(6.7)	11(12.2)	
	>or=60	4(7.6)	0(0)	2(6.7)	6(6.7)	
G	M	34(64.2)	6(85.7)	18(60)	58(64.4)	>0.05**
	F	19(35.9)	1(14.3)	12(40)	32(35.6)	
DD	<6 Mo	21(39.6)	1(14.3)	0(0)	22(36.7)	>0.05**
	6 Mo-1Y	14(26.4)	3(42.9)	0(0)	17(28.3)	
	>1 Y	18(34)	3(42.9)	0(0)	21(35)	

BMI=Body Mass Index, SM=Smoking, AL=Alcoholism, FH=Family History, AG=Age Group, G=Gender, DD=Disease Duration, UW=Under Weight, NW=Normal Weight, OW=Over Weight, O=Obese, M=Male, F=Female, Mo=Month, Y=Year, *=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Table II. Association of different variables with the incidence of *Hp*-associated diseases

Variables/HPP		GS (n=28)	GU (n=8)	DU (n=17)	Total (n=53)	<i>p</i> -value
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
BMI	U W	0(0)	0(0)	1(5.9)	1(1.9)	<0.05*
	NW	16(57.1)	3(37.5)	10(58.8)	29(54.7)	
	OW	10(35.7)	0(0)	4(23.5)	14(26.4)	
	O	2(7.1)	5(62.5)	2(11.8)	9(17)	
SM	Present	12(42.9)	2(25)	8(47.1)	22(41.5)	>0.05**
	Absent	16(57.1)	6(75)	9(52.9)	31(58.5)	
AL	Present	2(7.1)	0(0)	1(5.9)	3(5.7)	>0.05**
	Absent	26(92.9)	8(100)	16(94.1)	50(94.3)	
FH	Present	13(46.4)	2(25)	5(29.4)	20(37.7)	>0.05**
	Absent	15(53.6)	6(75)	12(70.6)	33(62.3)	
AG	18-29	12(42.9)	1(12.5)	6(35.3)	19(35.9)	>0.05**
	30-39	6(21.4)	2(25)	5(29.4)	13(24.5)	
	40-49	4(14.3)	3(37.5)	2(11.8)	9(17)	
	50-59	5(17.9)	1(12.5)	2(11.8)	8(15.1)	
	>or=60	1(3.6)	1(12.5)	2(11.8)	4(7.6)	
G	M	20(71.4)	2(25)	12(70.6)	34(64.2)	<0.05*
	F	8(28.6)	6(75)	5(29.4)	19(35.9)	
DD	<6 Mo	12(42.9)	3(37.5)	6(35.3)	21(39.6)	>0.05**
	6 Mo-1Y	7(25)	3(37.5)	4(23.5)	14(26.4)	
	>1 Y	9(32.1)	2(25)	7(41.2)	18(34)	

BMI=Body Mass Index, SM=Smoking, AL=Alcoholism, FH=Family History, AG=Age Group, G=Gender, DD=Disease Duration, UW=Under Weight, NW=Normal Weight, OW=Over Weight, O=Obese, M=Male, F=Female, Mo=Month, Y=Year, *=Significant and **=Not Significant.

Table III. Diagnosis of the *Hp*

Tests/Patients		GS	GU	DU	Total
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)
Combo Test	ve+	24(75)	6(75)	14(70)	44(73.3)
	ve-	8(25)	2(25)	6(30)	16(26.7)
	Total	32(100)	8(100)	20(100)	60(100)
Anti- <i>Hp</i> IgG	ve+	27(84.4)	8(100)	16(80)	51(85)
	ve-	5(15.6)	0(0)	4(20)	9(15)
	Total	32(100)	8(100)	20(100)	60(100)
Histopathology	ve+	21(65.6)	8(100)	11(55)	40(66.7)
	ve-	11(34.4)	0(0)	9(45)	20(33.3)
	Total	32(100)	8(100)	20(100)	60(100)
Final Diagnosis	ve+	28(87.5)	8(100)	17(85)	53(88.3)
	ve-	4(12.5)	0(0)	3(15)	7(11.7)
	Total	32(100)	8(100)	20(100)	60(100)

Table IV. Primary endoscopic and histopathological diagnosis

Endoscopic /Histopathological Diagnosis			Histopathology		Total	P-value
			GS			
			ve+	ve-		
			FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
Endoscopy	GS	ve+	11(34.3)	0(0)	11(34.3)	<0.05*
		ve-	21(65.7)	0(0)	21(65.7)	
	Total		32(100)	0(0)	32(100)	
Endoscopy	Sensitivity		39.2			
	Specificity		100			
	PPV		100			
	NPV		19			
Endoscopic /Histopathological Diagnosis			Histopathology		Total	Matching Between Endoscopy and Histopathology
			GS			
			ve+	ve-		
			FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
Endoscopy	GU		8(100)	0(0)	8(100)	Fully Matched
	DU		20(100)	0(0)	20(100)	
	Total		28(100)	0(0)	28(100)	

PPV=Positive Predictive Value, NPV=Negative Predictive Value and * =Significant.

Table V. Distribution of the HPP and PC groups according to primary endoscopic findings

Endoscopic Findings/Groups		HPP	PC	Total
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)
GS		11(20.7)	0(0)	11(18.3)
GU		8(15.1)	0(0)	8(13.3)
DU		17(32.1)	3(42.8)	20(33.3)
Others	GORD	0(0)	2(28.6)	2(3.3)
	Oesophageal Ulcer	1(1.9)	0(0)	1(1.7)
	Duodenitis	1(1.9)	0(0)	1(1.7)
	Lax Cardia	1(1.9)	0(0)	1(1.7)
	Gastropathy	11(20.7)	2(28.6)	13(21.7)
	Normal	3(5.7)	0(0)	3(5)
Total		53(100)	7(100)	60(100)

Table VI. Endoscopic findings in the duodenum and oesophagus for the HPP and PC groups

Endoscopic Findings/Groups		HPP	PC	Total
		FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)
D1	Normal	29(54.7)	4(57.1)	33(55)
	Erosive	2(3.8)	1(14.3)	3(5)
	Polyps and Stenosis	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Duodenitis	6(11.3)	0(0)	6(10)
	Ulcers	16(30.2)	2(28.6)	18(30)
	Total	53(100)	7(100)	60(100)
D2	Normal	44(83)	6(85.7)	50(83.4)
	Erosive	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Polyps and Stenosis	3(5.7)	0(0)	3(5)
	Duodenitis	5(9.4)	0(0)	5(8.3)
	Ulcers	1(1.9)	1(14.3)	2(3.3)
	Total	53(100)	7(100)	60(100)
Oesophagus	Normal	41(77.4)	3(42.9)	44(73.4)
	Erosive	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Lax Cardia	8(15.1)	0(0)	8(13.3)
	GORD	4(7.5)	4(57.1)	8(13.3)
	Total	53(100)	7(100)	60(100)

Table VII. Distribution of the HPP and PC groups according to endoscopic pathological features

Endoscopic Features/Groups	HPP	PC	Total	<i>P-value</i>
	FR(%)	FR(%)	FR(%)	
Nodularity and Polyps	3(5.7)	1(14.3)	4(6.7)	>0.05**
Haemorrhagic and Erythema	7(13.2)	0(0)	7(11.6)	
Congestion and Oedema	4(7.5)	0(0)	4(6.7)	
Erosion	4(7.5)	0(0)	4(6.7)	
Mosaic-like Pattern	1(1.9)	0(0)	1(1.7)	
Normal Description	34(64.2)	6(85.7)	40(66.6)	
Total	53(100)	7(100)	60(100)	

**=Not Significant.

الخلاصة

عدوى اللولبية البوابية لها انتشار واسع في العالم. تستعمر البكتريا اكثر من نصف سكان العالم وتعتبر السبب الرئيسي للالتهاب المعدي، التقرح الهضمي، السرطان الغدي المعدي و ورم الغدد للمفاوية المعدي. الاستجابة المناعية للمضيف غير قادرة على ازالة العدوى ويمكن ان تسهم فعلا في تولد المرض، كذلك العوامل الفتاكة الجرثومية كان لها دور معين في امراضه العدوى كما قيل من قبل دراسات محدودة وان السلالات الموجبة ل (*CagA*) ربما تكون مصحوبة بإصابات عنيفة.

وقد تم تصميم هذه الدراسة لتوضح بطريقة شاملة طبيعة الامراض المرتبطة باللولبية البوابية بين مجموعة من المرضى العراقيين. وهذا يشمل تقدير معدل انتشار اصابة اللولبية البوابية بين المرضى الذين خضعوا لناظور الجهاز الهضمي (OGD) والأشخاص الاصحاء. هذا المعدل لإصابة اللولبية البوابية وارتباطه بشدة المرض رُبط مع العديد من علامات نشاط المرض كمستوى (*IL-17A*) المصلي ونسبة عد خلايا (T) التنظيمية في الدم المحيطي ونتائج النسيج المرضي والتكرار والمستوى المصلي لمستضدات الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية ونوع السلالة البكتيرية بدلالة وجود او عدم وجود (*CagA*) كعامل ضراوة. طبقت ايضا علاقات بين كل علامات نشاط المرض لتوضيح التأثيرات المتبادلة على بعضها البعض.

شملت الدراسة ٦٠ مريضاً ممن يراجعون وحدة التنظير في مستشفى الجهاز الهضمي والكبد التعليمي، خلال الفترة بين سبتمبر/أيلول ٢٠١٢ وفبراير/ شباط ٢٠١٣، بمدى عمر ١٨-٨٠ سنة، و ٣٠ فرداً من الأصحاء ظاهرياً (سيطرة سلبية) بمدى عمر ١٨-٦٥ سنة بعد اجتيازهم لمعايير الاستثناء لهذه الدراسة. كلا المجموعتين خضعوا لورقة بيانات الاستبيان

ومن ثم كل مريض خضع لناظور الجهاز الهضمي (OGD) و جمع ٢-٤ من قرصة الخزعة المخاطية، لغرض إعداد الشرائح المصبغة لفحص النسيج المرضى. وقد تم جمع الدم المحيطي من جميع أشخاص المجاميع الدراسية عن طريق ثقب الوريد الذي تم تقسيمه الى جزئين: الأول لعد الخلايا (T) التنظيمية (CD4⁺ CD25⁺) الانسيابي، والثاني للاختبارات المصلية، التي تضمنت: اختبار المناعة اللوني المشطي السريع لأضداد اللولبية البوابية واختبار أضداد اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG) واختبار أضداد (CagA) نوع (IgG) واختبار أضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية نوع (IgG) واختبار (IL-17A) باستخدام تقنية (ELISA).

تم تقسيم المجموعة المرضية إلى مجموعتين: الأولى تضمنت ٥٣ مريضاً باللولبية البوابية (شملت ٢٨ مريضاً بالالتهاب المعدي، ٨ مرضى بقرحة المعدة و ١٧ مريضاً بقرحة الاثني عشري)، الثانية تضمنت ٧ مرضى كسيطرة ايجابية (شملت ٤ مرضى بالالتهاب المعدي، ٠ بقرحة المعدة و ٣ بقرحة الاثني عشري). كانت تكرارات الالم الشر سوفي/حرقه القلب وغثيان/تقي تمثل أعلى العلامات والأعراض بين مرضى اللولبية البوابية و مرضى السيطرة الايجابية، بينما كان الإسهال هو الأقل من بين كلا المجموعتين. الاختلافات في الاعراض الموجودة بين المجموعتين لم تكن معنوية ($p > 0.05$)، ماعدا فقدان الوزن، وهذه النتيجة كانت صحيحة بالنسبة لجميع المجاميع الفرعية لمرضى اللولبية البوابية. وفيما يتعلق بنتائج النسيج المرضي، تكرارات الالتهاب المعدي المزمن النشط والحؤول المعوي والاستعمار الجرثومي كانت أعلى معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) في مجموعة مرضى اللولبية البوابية مقارنةً بمجموعة مرضى السيطرة الموجبة، ولكن لم تكن هناك فروق معنوية ($p > 0.05$) في تكرارات كل نوع من انواع التهاب المعدة النسيجي بين المجاميع الفرعية لمرضى اللولبية البوابية. وبالتناقض مع هذا، تكرار الحؤول المعوي كان أعلى معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) ضمن

المجموعة الفرعية لمرضى قرحة المعدة بالمقارنة مع غيرها من المجاميع الفرعية لمرضى اللولبية البوابية، بينما تكرر الاستعمار البكتيري كان اقل معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) في المجموعة الفرعية لمرضى قرحة الاثني عشري بالمقارنة مع غيرها من المجاميع الفرعية لمرضى اللولبية البوابية. تكرارات و/او المعدل العياري لأضداد اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG) وأضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية كانت معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) مرتفعة في مجموعة مرضى اللولبية البوابية مقارنة مع السيطرة. بينما لم تكن هناك فروق معنوية ($p > 0.05$) بين المجاميع الفرعية لمرضى الالتهاب المعدي ومرضى قرحة المعدة فيما يتعلق بالتكرارات الإيجابية والمعدل المعياري لأضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية. على أية حال، أظهرت المجموعة الفرعية لمرضى قرحة الاثني عشري انخفاضا معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) في تكرر النتائج الموجبة لأضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية بالمقارنة مع المجموعات الفرعية الأخرى لمرضى اللولبية البوابية. تكرارات ومعدل العد/العياري لخلايا الدم المحيطي (T) التنظيمية ومستوى (IL-17A) المصلي أظهرت ارتفاعاً معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) في مجموعة مرضى اللولبية البوابية مقارنة بمجموعة السيطرة السلبية، ولكن لم تسجل أي فروقاً معنوية ($p > 0.05$) لهذه العلامات بين المجاميع الفرعية لمرضى اللولبية البوابية وكذلك بين الحالات السالبة والموجبة لأضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية. نسبة خلايا (T) التنظيمية: (IL-17A) كانت مرتفعة في مرضى اللولبية البوابية مقارنةً بكلا مجموعتي السيطرة. الفرق في التكرار ما بين ($CagA^-$) و ($CagA^+$) كان معنوياً في مجموعتي مرضى اللولبية البوابية والسيطرة السالبة ($p < 0.05$)، الذي كان صحيحاً لمجاميع مرضى اللولبية البوابية الفرعية، ما عدا مرضى قرحة الاثني عشري الذين اظهروا نتيجة غير معنوية ($p > 0.05$). على اية حال، لم يلاحظ أي فرق معنوي ($p > 0.05$) ما بين سلالات ($CagA^+$) و ($CagA^-$) بشأن المعلمات المذكورة اعلا، فيما

عدا ايجابية أضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية حيث كانت أعلى معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) بين أشخاص ($CagA^-$) من أشخاص ($CagA^+$) وإيجابية أضداد اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG) التي أظهرت عكس هذه النتيجة. لم تكن هناك فروقاً معنوية ($p > 0.05$) لجميع المعلمات المناعية المستخدمة من قبل هذه الدراسة في وجود أو عدم وجود الحؤول المعوي ونوع التهاب المعدة النسيجي، ولكن فرقاً معنوياً ($p < 0.05$) قد لوحظ في رؤية البكتريا بين النتائج الايجابية والسلبية لأضداد الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية. لم يسجل فرقاً معنوياً ($p > 0.05$) بين تكرار رؤية البكتريا (الاستعمار) ووجود أو عدم وجود الحؤول المعوي لجميع انواع التهاب المعدة النسيجي.

استنتاجات هذه الدراسة تشير إلى إن تكرار إصابة اللولبية البوابية في الاصحاء الظاهريون و/أو المصابون ولكن بدون اعراض من الأشخاص الذين شملوا في هذه الدراسة كان ٥٣,٣%، وهو اقل بكثير من تلك المتوفرة في السكان الآسيويين وغير الآسيويين. من ناحية اخرى، كان المعدل ٨٨,٣% في الأشخاص المصابين ممن راجعوا المستشفى المذكور أعلاه، الذين لديهم أعراض وهو مماثل لتلك الموجودة في معظم السكان الآسيويين وغير الآسيويين. الألم الشر سوفي وحرقة القلب هما اكثر العلامات/الاعراض شيوعاً بين اعتلال الامعاء المعدي المتعلق باللولبية البوابية وغير المتعلق بها. من ناحية أخرى، كان فقدان الوزن هو العرض الوحيد باختلاف معنوي بين مجموعتي اعتلال الأمعاء المعدي، وهذا الاستنتاج كان صحيحاً بالنسبة للمجاميع الفرعية لمرضى اللولبية البوابية. الكشف عن اعداد اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG) في مصل مرضى القناة الهضمية مفيد في تجنب الاختبارات التشخيصية الاكثر اجتياحاً كالتنظير والخزعة، لكن مستوى اعداد اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG) في المصل لا ينبأ بحدوث التقرحات الهضمية او كثافة استعمار اللولبية البوابية.

معظم مرضى اللولبية البوابية اظهروا مستوى عالي من (IL-17A) وعد خلايا الدم المحيطي (T) التنظيمية. نسبة خلايا (T) التنظيمية: (IL-17A) أعلى في مجموعة مرضى اللولبية البوابية من مجاميع السيطرة الايجابية والسلبية، وهذا يثبت ان الاستجابة المناعية تكون غير فعالة في مرضى اللولبية البوابية بسبب تعداد خلايا (T) التنظيمية الذي يكون مهيمناً على معيارية (IL-17A). تفشي أضرار الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية كان ٢٠% في الناس الاصحاء و/او المصابون ولكن بدون اعراض و ٣٠,٢% في مرضى اللولبية البوابية وهذا يشير الى وجود علاقة ايجابية هامة بين اصابة اللولبية البوابية والمناعة الذاتية المعدية. وجود اضرار الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية قد يتزامن مع مستوى وقائي لنشوء قرحة الاثني عشري. تعداد خلايا الدم المحيطي (T) التنظيمية ومستوى (IL-17A) المصلي لم يبدوا أي تأثيراً معنوياً على ايجابية اضرار الخلايا الجدارية الذاتية والحمل البكتيري والحؤول المعوي ونوع التهاب المعدة النسيجي. انتشار اضرار (CagA) نوع (IgG) بين الناس العراقيين الايجابيين لأضرار اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG) كان ٣٧,٣% وهو اقل بكثير من معظم الدراسات العالمية الاخرى. وجود سلالة اللولبية البوابية نوع ($CagA^+$) لا يكفي للتنبؤ بنوع المرض المتعلق باللولبية البوابية وكذلك بشدة المرض. على أية حال، سلالات ($CagA^+$) تلعب دوراً في تعديل الاستجابة المناعية من خلال اظهار معيار عالي من اضرار اللولبية البوابية نوع (IgG). نوع سلالة اللولبية البوابية له تأثير قليل وغير معنوي على مستوى (IL-17A) وتعداد خلايا (T) التنظيمية في المرضى المصابين بالأمراض المتعلقة باللولبية البوابية. سم الخلايا (CagA) ليس له دور في تحريض التهاب المعدة المناعي الذاتي المتعلق باللولبية البوابية وليس له ارتباطاً مع بعض النتائج النسيجية المرضية مثل نوع التهاب المعدة النسيجي وجود او عدم وجود الحؤول المعوي والكثافة البكتيرية في مقاطع

المعدة المصبوغة.النتائج النسيجية المذكورة ليس لها ارتباطا مع مستوى أضداد اللولبية
البوابيه نوع (IgG) أو ايجابيه أضداد الخلايا الجداريه الذاتية، ماعدا الاستعمار البكتيري له
دور ثابت في تحريض المرض المناعي الذاتي المذكور.

هيئة التعليم التقني

كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد

قرار لجنة المناقشة

نحن أعضاء لجنة المناقشة نشهد بأننا قد اطلعنا على الرسالة الموسومة (نزعة التعديل المناعي الخلطية و الخلوية في الأمراض المعد - معوية المستحدثة ببكتريا اللولبية البوابية) وناقشنا الطالب (حسن عبد علي خضير) في محتوياتها وفيما له علاقة بها وفي ضوء ذلك وجد بأنه جديراً بنيل درجة الماجستير التقني في اختصاص تقنيات التحليلات المرضية.

التوقيع:

رئيس اللجنة: د. غانم حسين مجيد

المرتبة العلمية: أستاذ مساعد

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التوقيع:

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عميد الكلية

التاريخ: ٢٠١٤/٨/٢

هيئة التعليم التقني

كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد

م/إقرار المشرف

نحن الأستاذ المساعد (د. مضاء محمد شيت) والاستشاري (د. جاسم محسن غضبان) المشرفان على رسالة طالب الماجستير (حسن عبد علي خضير) بموجب الأمر الإداري المرقم (٥١٦٤/٣) والمؤرخ في (٢٠١٢/١٢/١٠)، قد اطلعنا على رسالة الطالب المذكور والتي أنجزت تحت إشرافنا، نقر ونؤيد صلاحيتها للمناقشة لاستيفائها كافة المتطلبات العلمية لنيل درجة الماجستير التقني.

التوقيع:

المشرف: د. جاسم محسن غضبان

المرتبة العلمية: استشاري

التاريخ: ٢٠١٤/ ١ / ٢

التوقيع:

المشرف: د. مضاء محمد شيت

المرتبة العلمية: أستاذ مساعد

التاريخ: ٢٠١٤/ ١ / ٢

م/إقرار المقوم اللغوي

إني الأستاذ المساعد (د. رعد شاكر النواس) المقوم اللغوي لرسالة طالب الماجستير (حسن عبد علي خضير) الموسومة (نزعة التعديل المناعي الخاطية و الخلوية في الأمراض المعد - معوية المستحدثة ببكتريا التولبية البوابية)، اقر وأؤيد سلامتها اللغوية وصلاحيتها للمناقشة لاستيفائها كافة متطلبات هذا الجانب.

التوقيع:

المقوم اللغوي: د. رعد شاكر النواس

المرتبة العلمية: أستاذ مساعد

التاريخ: ٢٠١٣/ ١٢ / ٣١

م/مصادقة

إني رئيس قسم تقنيات التحليلات المرضية في كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية، أصادق على إقرار المشرف على رسالة طالب الماجستير التقني (حسن عبد علي خضير) وعلى إقرار المقوم اللغوي، واعتبر الرسالة صالحة للمناقشة من قبل اللجنة الممتحنة المشكلة لهذا الغرض.

التوقيع:

د. ميادة نوري إقبال

أستاذ مساعد

رئيس قسم تقنيات التحليلات المرضية

التاريخ: ٢٠١٤/ ١ / ٢

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
هيئة التعليم التقني
كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية/بغداد

نزعة التعديل المناعي الخلطية و الخلوية في الأمراض المعد - معوية المستحدثة ببكتريا اللولبية البوابية

رسالة مقدمة إلى

مجلس كلية التقنيات الصحية والطبية

كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجة الماجستير التقني في تقنيات التحليلات المرضية

من قبل

حسن عبد علي خضير

بكالوريوس تحليلات مرضية (٢٠١١)

بإشراف

د.جاسم محسن غضبان

استشاري متخصص

بالمعدة والأمعاء والكبد

د.مضاء محمد شيت

أستاذ مساعد

صفر/١٤٣٥ هـ

كانون الأول/٢٠١٣ م